

NEON -Next Generation Integrated Energy Services for Citizen Energy Communities

WP 1- Integrated energy service co-creation and cross-sectoral arrangements

D1.2 Service offer Co-creation and business planning

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Abstract:	<p>This task is responsible for specification of NEON service offer, underlying servitization approach and preliminary business planning by involving relevant actors in the discussion, including the consumers, service providers, and grid stakeholders. As part of it, relevant actors will be engaged in service co-creation process that resulted in specification of underlying service concepts, identification of revenue opportunities and set-up of financial mechanisms.</p> <p>The report presents the results of co-creation process among involved stakeholders aimed to set the underlying service concepts and perform preliminary business planning.</p>
Keyword List:	Stakeholders, Co-creation process, energy efficiency services, offer, business opportunities, business plan

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Editor(s):	Philippe Calvez
Contributor(s):	Sergio Lujan, Michel Meunier, Simona D'oca, Sara De la serna, Alessandro Asmundo, Chiara Lemmi, Raphaelle Papa, Sara Tari Lilia Bouchendouka.
Reviewer(s):	Valentina Janev, Eneko Olabarrieta.
Approved by:	
Recommended/mandatory readers:	Valentina Janev, Eneko Olabarrieta, Philippe Calvez.

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Name	Partner
Alessandro Asmundo	SIF
ALET Pierre-Jean	CSEM
Chiara Lemmi	SIF
Cintia Escandell García	COM
Eneko Olabarrieta	R2M
Giulia Carbonari	R2M Energy
Gonzalo Navarrete	TRAZA
Kiriaki Psara	FOSS
Lilia Bouchendouka	ENGIE
Michel Meunier	ALB
Nikola Tomasevic	IMP
Paula Jimenez	TRAZA
Philippe Calvez	ENGIE
Sara Delaserna	IDAE
Sara Ruffini	R2M Energy
Sara Tari	SIF
Sergio Lujan	GFM
Sergio Velasquez	COM
Simona Doca	GRA
Valentina Janev	IMP
Venizelos Efthymiou	FOSS

Executive summary

This report presents the service offer specification and business models for each NEON use case created as a result of the co-creation process with stakeholders of each Citizen Energy Community, including the consumers, municipalities, service providers and grid stakeholders.

The business models focus on service offer for energy efficiency and flexibility, enabling cross-service integration, and deliver optimal energy assets scheduling and building control.

The report is structured in five main sections. The first section introduces the **concept of a co-creation process**, as a collaborative practice that gives the ability to collectively produce a shared vision of things and to co-develop new value. Such a practice allows the exploration of the possibilities through the eyes, needs and creativity of participants who differ from each other in terms of professions, experiences, and expectations. The process comprises the five phases shown in the image below, where interviews and collaborative workshops with stakeholders were key for development of the services and business models.

The second section presents **NEON services co-creation framework**, that allowed a coordinated and consistent approach across pilots. It comprised three stages: planning, individual interviews, and collaborative frameworks. The planning stage determines who will participate in the cocreation process and the main actors for the interviews, followed by the individual interviews to understand the main actors' activities, partners, energy uses, needs, expectations and pains, as well as analysis to extract key data. Finally, the collaborative workshops allowed to share task 1.1 results, co-identify, and prioritize opportunities for the CEC thanks to an impact-effort matrix and describe the quick-wins opportunities through a Business Model Canvas (BMC), having as the main outcome the identification of business opportunities and their description and planification.

The third section presents **stakeholders' interviews results**. A common protocol and an interview guide were provided for all interviews with key information (type of interview, duration, deadline, the required material and tools, the process and recommended timing). There was a wide variety of stakeholder types, from DSOs, through municipalities, local industries, and SMEs to citizens. The report presents the results of the interviews in a matrix of stakeholders mapping the opportunities and difficulties for the

materialization of the proposed services and business models. A Citizen Energy Community (CEC) map on the interaction between the different agents (services back and front end, customers, and users) is also presented for each pilot.

The fourth section focuses on **NEON CECs service co-creation sessions**. As a first step, a common protocol was provided for all the pilots, with key information to carry out the collaborative workshop, including two main templates. Firstly, an effort-impact matrix to position all the services opportunities and identify the quick-wins within the NEON project and secondly, a complete Business Model Canvas (BMC) to make a business description of these quick-wins, which includes the potential benefits and to whom they impact, who provides them, partners, required activities to create and deliver the service, available means, costs structure and revenue stream. The workshops were carried out in a sequential manner: ideas generation, their selection and prioritization, opportunities description and finally, drafting an initial business plan. For each pilot, conclusions were reached, and drivers identified. In Berchidda the surging energy costs were identified as a driver to create an energy community that could leverage energy independence while, on the other hand, there were some concerns related to the benefit of the community. In Domaine de la Source, next steps for techno-economic and legal analysis were identified, as well as the needs on buildings and IT expertise. In Polígono industrial de las cabezas two opportunities with high impact and low effort were identified: PV self-consumption and storage systems. Finally, Stains city highlighted the complexity nature of CECs, which in some aspects require significant technical and human efforts difficult to reach within the timescales of the project.

The final section presents the **conclusions**. The co-creation process was successful in identifying potential services and business models for each pilot, benefiting from insights from the key stakeholders.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

AHU	Air Handling Unit
BMC	Business model Canvas
DDLS	Domaine De La Source
DSO	Distribution System Operator
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
EV	Electric Vehicle
FCEV	Fuel Cell Electric Vehicle
NDT	Non-destructive Testing
PV	Photovoltaic generation
P2G	Power to Gas
WP	Work package

Introduction

This task managed to specify existing and potential services and plan business models of each Citizen Energy Community (CEC) in a co-creation process with stakeholders. A servitization approach was integrated, forwarding preliminary business planning in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders such as end-users, service providers, and grid stakeholders.

The objectives of this task were the following:

- 1 Carry out the work initiated in task 1.1
- 2 Begin to co-ideate possible services designed in the lifetime of the Neon project
- 3 Describe the service co-ideated from a business model perspective

To carry out these objectives, a co-creation process was defined composed of interviews and a collaborative workshop with stakeholders. Citizen Energy Community leaders conducted this process, reflecting the mutual agreement on effective service offer for energy efficiency and flexibility exploitation, as well as on the leveraging service concepts to enable cross-service integration, and deliver optimal energy assets scheduling and building control.

This task has also been coordinated along with task 1.4, which intends to match services with end-users' requirements with the design of services. These two tasks worked together to design the field work and approach to end-users to understand their needs, motivations, energy practices, and better design services that will be valuable for them. The exchange of results and capitalization of these, showed to be very valuable.

Conclusions made by involved stakeholders serve as an important and strong baseline of services ideation to conduct activities relevant to the following work packages.

1. Structure and implementation

Regarding the work plan of the task, ENGIE organized a coherent workflow of tasks that included the collaboration of a multi-disciplinary team. The tasks carried out were the following:

Tasks	
01	Stakeholders' identification and mapping
02	Co-creation process methodology definition
02	prepare the key stakeholders contact list, using Template for the actors list included with the process description document
03	preparation of the stakeholders' interviews by using the objectives, process, and templates provided
04	realize all the interviews of the stakeholders' main actors
05	Stakeholders' interviews analysis
06	collaborative workshop preparation (process on the co-creation document)
07	conduct the collaborative workshop with all the stakeholders

08	share the co-creation process results with the NEON project participants
09	elaborate the business planning for the services opportunities
10	D1.2 report submission

Table 1 T1.2 major milestones

As an approach to the task’s objectives, CEC leaders mapped the stakeholders in order to acknowledge the different types of actors involved. Further, and leveraging the expertise of different partners involved, an ambitious and detailed co-creation process methodology was defined. This included a guide for CEC leaders to implement the methodology, template to conduct interviews and participatory dynamics to conduct creative thinking workshops with stakeholders of each CEC. Once it was developed and contrasted with CEC leaders and other involved partners, the methodology was implemented. Finally, the strategic and qualitative results were analysed and employed to elaborate business planning service opportunities.

2. Co-creation concept definition

As part of the WP1 “Integrated energy service co-creation and cross-sectoral arrangements “, the Task 1.2 focused on the “co-creation” phase with the aim to generate services offer specification and business planning for each NEON use case separately.

The task objectives were to identify NEON stakeholders, to evaluate their needs as well as to include them in the services opportunities’ identification and specification. Hence, NEON organized a series of workshops to engage NEON pilots’ stakeholders in the services and business co-creation.

Co-creation is a collaborative practice that gives the ability to collectively produce a shared vision of things and to co-develop new value. Such a practice allows exploration of the possibilities through the eyes, needs and creativity of participants who differ from each other in terms of professions, experiences, and expectations. To implement it, NEON consortium has defined a co-creation process and methodology that will be detailed in the next section of this report. To be effective, the co-creation process must be carried out through individual and collective phases alternately to understand the context and the different points of view, then to collectively generate a maximum of ideas which are then prioritized and modeled / described. It is therefore based on existing methodologies such as:

<http://groupquality.com/agile-co-creation-as-a-service/co-creation-steps/>

This diagram presents an example of an inspiring co-creation process for our work:

- The first step (ENGAGE) concentrates on meeting and discovering the stakeholders of the project i.e., pilots of the NEON project. In this phase, it is important to know them better, identify their context, habits, and main expectations. It also makes it possible to start involving them (individually) in the co-creation process.
- The second step (UNDERSTAND) is a stage of consolidation and analysis of the collected data. This enables an initial assessment of the benefits, needs, and pains which will be useful in the following phases.
- The third step (IDEATION) is a collaborative phase. It relies on collective intelligence. Brainstorming and group exercises allow emergence of many ideas and solutions that address the needs and pains (that have been shared upstream).
- The fourth step (DEFINE) brings together the data and ideas from the previous steps to clearly define and prioritize the solutions to be implemented.
- The last step (VALIDATE) allows these solutions to be tested and validated regarding the initial needs. The final objective is to launch their development and to make them available to the stakeholders.

In the next section, the co-creation framework that was created to meet the specific requirements of the NEON project will be presented in detail.

3. NEON services co-creation framework

The process started by establishing and verifying the list of participants, present at the workshop. Then, the group worked on the first version of the co-creation framework that each NEON use case leader would have to implement on their own.

Partner	Role
ENGIE	Task leader /CEC leader-France
ALB	ESCO and CEC leader-France
R2M	Replication expert
GRA	CEC leader-Italy
SIF	Financial expert
IDAE	Legal expert
APPA (GFM)	CEC leader-Spain
FOSS	Methodology
CSEM	Energy efficiency applications expert
IMP	System integration expert
TRAZA(IPV)	Collaborative methodologies expert
COM	Communication and end user experience

Table 2 T1.2 participants roles

The main objective of this framework was to involve all the actors of each use case in the identification and description of the services that will be useful to them. The business description and technical specification of these opportunities will be an input of the next tasks.

The framework is based on:

- The co-definition of a co-creation methodology (list of participants, process, steps, and tools),
- The establishment of the co-creation phase agenda (deadlines, dependencies, and intermediate meetings)
- The provision a set of protocols and templates to each use case leader.

The co-creation process has been represented as follows

Figure 1 NEON's co-creation framework

This co-creation process is based on three macro steps:

1st macro-step → planning:

1. Analysis of the task T1.1 stakeholders map regarding the co-creation objectives,
2. Identification of the key actors within each stakeholder group (= who will participate?),
3. Scheduling of each main actors' interviews and planning of a collaborative workshop with all the use case stakeholders once interviews are completed and analyzed.

2nd macro-step → individual interviews:

1. adaption the co-creation tools and templates provided by the Task leader,
2. Customization of these tools and templates, if necessary (e.g., Translation into Spanish, or Italian),
3. Performing the interviews to understand the main actors' activities, partners, energy uses, needs and expectations, pains...
 - a. explain the co-creation and interview objectives and process.
 - b. ask them to describe their existing activities and actors / collaborators.
 - c. ask them to describe their existing energy uses.
 - d. identify pain points, needs, and desires.
 - e. explain the next steps (opportunity to get everybody involved in the co-creation process).
4. Consolidation of the interviews thanks to the interviewers note taking and recordings,
5. Analysis of the interviews to extract key data, common needs and pains, ideas / opportunities to be discussed, etc.

3rd macro-step → collaborative workshop:

1. Preparation of the workshop (physical and digital) supports based on the proposed templates,
2. Facilitation of the workshop (T1.1 results sharing, interviews results sharing, new opportunities discussion and prioritization, quick-win descriptions),
 - a. share the interviews results / main insights
 - b. share the T1.1 results (cross-integrated services)
 - c. compare the stakeholders' activities, energy uses, pain points and needs
 - d. co-identify and prioritize opportunities for the CEC thanks to an impact-effort matrix
 - e. describe the quick-wins opportunities thanks to a Business Model Canvas
3. Consolidation of the workshop results in terms of opportunities business description and planification
4. Finalization of the co-creation process deliverables.

As the main deliverables of the co-creation process implementation, ENGIE, as a task leader has proposed the following:

1. Stakeholders' map and main actors list (name and contact information)
2. Interviews and collaborative workshop agenda
3. Interviews' annotations (and registration authorizations)
4. Stakeholders' pain points and needs map
5. T1.1 simplified BMC completed with the interviews' insights

6. Workshop annotations and photos
7. CEC's opportunities list
8. CEC's opportunities impact-effort matrix
9. Quick-wins description through a Business Model Canvas

ENGIE and the CEC leaders created an initial schedule in the form of a Gantt chart to present not only the tasks to be carried out but also their dependencies from mid-January to mid-April 2022.

- Before January 14th: the task leader proposed a first co-creation process to all the pilots' leaders and thus workshop to finalize this process with the contribution of all the pilots' leaders.
- Before January 21st: planification of the stakeholders' main actors' interviews (between Jan.28th and Feb. 18th) and global workshop (between March 11th and March 25th).
- Before January 28th: preparation of the stakeholders' interviews by using the objectives, process and templates provided.
- Before February 18th: conduct all the interviews of the stakeholders' main actors'.
- Before March 4th: analyze the stakeholders' interviews and extract insights (Stakeholders' pain points and needs map + T1.1 simplified BMC completed).
- Before March 11th: prepare the collaborative workshop by using the objectives, process and templates provided.
- Before March 25th: conduct the collaborative workshop with all the (future) CEC's stakeholders based on the T1.1 and the interviews results.
- Before April 8th: share the co-creation process results with the NEON project participants (sharing and enrichment for T1.2) .

Figure 2 NEON's co-creation process Gantt chart

This diagram also includes the main milestones for each NEON use cases and for the overall Task T1.2. To support the use case leaders and exchange ideas or propose solutions to potential challenges that might arise, the task leader offered to be involved in planning the use case specific meetings during each planification, preparation, and analysis steps. At the end of each preparation and analysis steps, ENGIE, as a task leader, organized T1.2 meetings to share ideas and analysis within the WP1 participants.

ENGIE performed a dedicated workshop with all the CEC leaders to present this framework proposal and get their feedback. It was essential that the participants to appropriate the process and agenda to be able to implement it within each of their CECs.

The framework has been validated during this NEON workshop and the task leader ENGIE worked on specific protocols and templates.

4. Stakeholder interviews results

The task leader has proposed a dedicated protocol to give some support to the use cases leaders.

This protocol gave the key information to carry out the interviews such as the type of interview, the duration, the deadline, the required material and tools, the process and recommended timing.

Interview type	<p>Semi-structured interview. This type of exploratory research is often used for qualitative purposes and consists of semi-structured questions that are prepared before the interview and serves as a guide. These questions are somewhat flexible and allowing key points of interest to emerge.</p> <p>In-person interviews are highly recommended, otherwise a video call can be arranged. Phone calls should be avoided or used as a last option.</p>
Participants	Main actor(s) of the (future) CEC's stakeholder
Deadline	Interviews must be conducted before February 15 th
Duration	60 min
Required material	Laptop, webcam (in case of a remote interview), recording device
Required supports	Survey / list of questions, registration authorization document
Process and timing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome the interviewee (5 min) • Explain the co-creation and interview objectives and process (5 min) • Ask the interviewee to describe their existing activities and main actors / collaborators (15 min) • Ask the interviewee to describe how they currently use energy. Invite them to do so by going through their daily routines (15 min) • Identity pain points, needs and opportunities during the discussion, and explore key aspects with follow-up questions (during 3. and 4.) • Share your understanding of their main pain point and needs and ask the interviewee to react (15 min) • Thank the participant(s) and recall the next step (the collaborative workshop before March 25th) (5 min)
Guide to conduct interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When you contact the (potential) stakeholder, and invite them to an interview, try to explain with simple words the purpose of the interview. Be flexible when choosing the time, date and place of the interview.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Don't be too strict with your questions, dig deeper to reveal what that person needs in terms of energy uses. If the answers are too general or short, ask more concrete questions that are simple and direct. Ask as many follow-up questions as needed! • A good way to get interviewees to identify and reveal their needs is to ask them about their routine (how do you normally use energy in your daily routine? Does this routine change in summer or winter? What about weekends?) • It's critical that in the interview notes you do not include personal opinions or interpretations, but literally what the interviewee commented on. If not, you will be contaminating the research. • Show great appreciation for accessing to give you an interview and communicate to him/her the importance of such as well as their (potential) participation in the CEC
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Table 3 Stakeholder interviews protocol

Then we created and proposed a complete interview guide with:

1. some elements to introduce the NEON project and the co-creation process,
2. the key questions to be asked during the interview about their activities, energy uses, partners, needs, pains, ideas, etc.,
3. elements for the interview conclusion based on the process next step,
4. templates to consolidate the key information needs and pains matrix, simplified BMC.

All use cases leaders were able to customize this guide for their own needs and thus lead this important step in the co-creation process.

The next sections describe the stakeholders' identification and interviews results for each use case.

4.1 CEC 01 -BERCHIDDA

For the citizen's interviews in the Berchidda pilot site, we followed the protocol illustrated in the previous section. In the week between the 4th – 10th April GridAbility performed five in-person interviews by phone, involving the representatives of the main stakeholders that will be implicated in the Berchidda CEC:

- **Azienda Elettrica Comunale (AEC) – Local DSO**
- **Berchidda Municipality**
- **Local industries**
- **Citizens**
- **SME**

STAKEHODER GROUP	CONTACT INFORMATION	DATE INTERVIEW
End user SME (President Giogantinu Winery)	By phone	04/02/2022 09:00
Local DSO	By phone	04/02/2022 10:00

End user (Citizen with PV production Family 4 with 2 kids)	By phone	04/02/2022 11:00
End user industry (Cork industry Colla & Fresu)	By phone	08/02/2022 09:30

Table 4 CEC01- interviews planning table

The interviews aimed at gathering the opinions of both the CEC front end services providers, as well as the final users.

Figure 3 CEC BERCHIDDA stakeholders mapping

Stakeholder name and type	Needs, Opportunities	Pains, Difficulties
End user SME (Giogantinu Winery)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The skyrocketing energy prices would be a stimulus towards the possibility of expanding the production in self-management. • To understand how to upgrade the photovoltaic. • Need to understand in how many years the investment would be recouped. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need to understand how to access funds for installation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concern about the electric bill due to high energy prices, as from next year, the estimates speak of an increase of 4 to 5 times the energy bill. • The increase in the cost of energy means an increase in the cost of the product sold (a problem shared with competitors) but that could be in our case a commercial competitive advantage.
Responsible energy services AEC (Local DSO)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The main expectation is a different management, with more professionalism. • The management of services for citizens with greater efficiency. • -The mayor has a project with a photovoltaic system with participation of the power plant (municipality buys the land and makes the investment). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local DSO still far from self-generation • Not enough PV installations, with the advent of the CEC there is a hope that there will be more awareness and new installations.
End user (Citizen With PV production Family 4 with 2 kids)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong close-knitted community, small village where everybody knows each other • Communications happen informally among the citizens • The PV installations are perceived as easy to manage. • The end users know what to (maintenance) do to keep production high. • The end users know what to do to better align consumption with production peak time • Energy community would be a dream, in terms of being able to provide energy at no cost with photovoltaics. • - Disagreement with wind energy, better to leave the skyline free in Sardinia. Solar panels are perceived as easier to hide or disguise in the countryside, and fields can be grazed anyway even with the panels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electricity has a big impact on the household budget • There is no gas connection in Berchidda, the space heating happens via diesel or biomass boilers • Storage batteries are not present in every home

<p>End user Cork industry (Colla & Fresu)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Good MANAGEMENT of shared resources ▪ We have installations for which different power is needed, being able to find a point of consumption and saving on the bill • To unbundle from the diesel plant, both for energy savings, as well as for health and environmental benefits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Now not involved in the CEC but have been contacted by the mayor to contribute. ▪ Do not have direct contact with the Municipality, nor participate in community events ▪ Concern about electricity grid • - The product sold cannot change price, the profit margin is reduced.
<p>Berchidda Municipality (Mayor)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The centrality of citizens in the management of energy at the municipal level is not only an act of ethics but also of environmental protection and sustainability. ▪ The relationships with key stakeholders are linked to the needs for innovation of the electricity service in support of the future CEC. ▪ Close cooperative relationships with several international research groups, mainly employed in the process of territorial animation. ▪ The Municipality of Berchidda is the owner of the electricity distribution, with a mandate that expires in 2030, and allows the Municipality to distribute electricity to the end user (role of DSO) ▪ The Municipality is investing in the Berchidda 4.0 Project as one of the first Energy Communities in Italy. ▪ The Municipality is investing to encourage local production of energy from PV. ▪ Future installations of wind farms in our territory are foreseen but not planned. ▪ The Municipality is spending 1.5 million euros for the construction of the new smart distribution network ▪ The Municipality is investing in the acquisition of the energy distribution grid in the agricultural area from Enel Distribution ▪ On the consumer side, the Municipality is working towards an increase in RES production systems and accumulation systems for the optimal management of production (also considering the presence of charging stations for electric vehicles), as well as towards the implementation of policies of active participation of the demand for electricity for the management of the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The main energy uses in Berchidda are household loads. This is being pursued as main pain point for the design of the service provision of the energy community. ▪ Structural deficit in renewable energy production, the Municipality has only 5 photovoltaic systems and about 60 private systems. ▪ The Municipality still records vast purchases of electricity from the main grid. ▪ The municipal electrical network is however obsolete, and the distribution plants are not adequate to accommodate the smart technology suitable for the construction and future management of community energy services ▪ To date there are national regulatory barriers for an entity to be both distributor and seller of energy. ▪ Difficulties of management and ordinary and extraordinary maintenance • Lack of professionalism and the lack of adequate technical and administrative skills that allow the Municipality to manage the development of the future Energy Community and the related energy services.

	<p>electricity grid obtained through the connection of second-generation bi-directional measurement systems.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The Municipality will soon establish a new DSO with total public capital of the Municipality of Berchidda, under which will be transferred the competence of energy distribution. The constitution of a company with public capital makes sense, because in this way the Municipality can also become a full part of and benefit from the shared management of energy within the CEC. ▪ The energy community needs to remain independent in the energy management. ▪ Citizen empowerment beyond the simple consumer, towards the formation of prosumers ▪ Civil and collective participation in the electricity system ▪ Progressive awareness that energy is a primary good 	
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Table 5 CEC 01-BERCHIDDA municipality Interviews results table

From the responses provided by the various stakeholders, it emerged that Berchidda has the fortune to be characterised by a community with a strong sense of sharing, sensitivity to sustainability and willingness to innovate. It is a small community where everyone knows each other and wants to act together for a more efficient centralised management of energy services, to eliminate fossil fuels and to boost local energy production from renewable sources, which is still considered too low now, to address the rising energy prices that have a strong impact on household budgets and to decrease the energy demand from the national grid that is still too high.

It is also actively supported by the municipality, which is owner and DSO of Berchidda’s grid, and which is investing heavily in projects and the development of the city's renewable smart grid with active participation of the population. They have high expectations from municipal, state, and European funding for the RES penetration, for the grid’s reinforcement, for the formation of the Renewable Energy Community and for support from professionals for its management and development.

4.2 CEC02 -DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE

Figure 4 CEC Domaine De La source stakeholders mapping

In Domaine de la Source (DDLs) stakeholders are, members of conseil syndical (CS committee), all residents and flat owner except ORPI which is the syndic (condominium managing agent). Among these persons some are very interested by the physics of energy in their building, and we have focused our interview on them.

We have two / three meetings, assembly (2) and personal meetings by phone.

Meeting date	Details
July 21 st , 2021	The first meeting (July 21) was just to know each person and to present Neon project.
Sept 21 st , 2021	The second meeting 6h (Sept 21) was to visit deeply the energy installation, to collect a lot of information and to discuss needs, pains, dreams, future of energy, Energy communities... This was the cocreation process.
Sept 21 ..April 22	#Phone calls

Table 6 CEC02- interviews planning table

After we have made a letter of intent, a sort of contract between **Albedo Energie** (ALB) and DDLs. This letter summarizes their expectations with Neon Project.

Below is the summarize of their main expectation within Neon project.

Stakeholder name and type	Needs, Opportunities	Pains, Difficulties
Flat owner 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve energy efficiency combining heating pumps, electric and gas boiler, hot water loop, electric melting snow, and solar power plant. • Measurement of energy system with sensors. • Analysis of energy efficiency and consumption. • What about the future of energy prices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of methodology and data for analysis efficiency, • Lack of measurement systems • Need to install sensors, • Energy price uncertainties.
Flat owner 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy costs reduction, • Comfort improvement air exhaust too noisy, • Develop self-consumption because the selling price is too low, • -We need an audit of the global energy system to improve it. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usage of energy is often not synchronized with energy production, • Lack of understanding of energy system.
Building manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To develop self-consumption and efficiency, • To value our solar power plant, • To extend the energy sharing to other buildings around us. • To get the support of the municipality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Even if the energy budget is low in the global expenses, the residence complex needs to anticipate the future, • EDF price solar energy buying price is too low, • We are early adopters and we wanted to show that we are adopting new technologies to create value for our building it.
Flat owner 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To developpe energy sharing allows us to build a community, • To make more for climate impact • To include electric mobility in the energy scope, • To understand more how to reduce energy consumption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To encourage our neighbour to share the importance of energy control, • To connect our future electric vehicle to the solar power plant

Table 7 CEC 02-DOMAINDE DE LA SOURCE interview results table

These interviews were more a technical meeting to understand how we can improve DDLS energy efficiency and self-consumption.

4.3 CEC 03- POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS

To carry out the interviews planned for task T1.2, it was followed the planning and protocol established by the NEON project consortium members. From 01st to 08th February 2022, GFM performed eleven

interviews to different stakeholders, both energy providers representative people and end user (electrical consumers and owners of electric vehicles).

In the following table we can see a little summary of interviewed agents. Due to data protection policy, some stakeholders' names are not provided.

STAKEHODER GROUP	CEC participant	Method of conducting the interview	Interview date
End user 1	Electrical consumer - residential	Phone	01/02/2022
End user 2	EV owner	Face to face	01/02/2022
End user 3	Electrical consumer - industrial	Phone	01/02/2022
End user 4	Electrical consumer - residential	Phone	02/02/2022
Energy provider 1	Energy provider – PV self-consumption (GFM)	Face to face	02/02/2022
End user 5	Electrical consumer - residential	Phone	02/02/2022
End user 6	Electrical consumer - residential	Face to face	03/02/2022
Energy provider 2	Energy provider – storage (GFM)	Face to face	04/02/2022
End user 7	Electrical consumer - industrial	Phone	04/02/2022
End user 8	EV owner	Phone	07/02/2022
Energy provider 3	Energy provider – EV recharging station (GFMCA)	Face to face	08/02/2022

Table 8 CEC 03 interviews planning table

Following CEC map is defined as a summary for description of different agents' interaction between themselves.

Figure 5 CEC03-POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL stakeholders mapping

Following results have been extracted from the interviews (see Annex 01):

Stakeholder name and type	Needs, Opportunities	Pains, Difficulties
Stakeholder 01 – End user 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of electricity prices, • Fixed prices for electricity, • Possibility of using the meter installed in the house, • Reduction of the consumed energy, • Reduction of electricity prices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High cost of electricity, • Electrical fluctuation due to the grid (possible devices damaging), • Existing smart meter for consumption monitoring cannot manage any device at home, neither locally nor remotely.

<p>Stakeholder 02 – End user 2</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of electricity prices • Energy for recharging EV • Recharging his electric vehicle using environmentally sustainable, • Regular consumer (EV recharging service), • Individual self-consumption with storage system at home, • Small portable recharging device for electric vehicles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possible EV recharging station damage • Reduced number of public EV recharging station.
<p>Stakeholder 03 – End user 3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEC deployment, • PV systems deployment, • Bringing renewable systems closer to local people, • Saving money • NEON consortium member, • PV self-consumption system shared by free with other stakeholders, • Possibility of loads managing, • Regular and predictable consumption. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced money saving due to shared self-consumption system, • High Electricity prices, • Stakeholders understanding.
<p>Stakeholder 04 – End user 4</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of electricity prices. • As small consumer, end user impact is not important. But it would help to get the CEC growth. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High cost of electricity • Rising electricity prices tendency • There is not any consumption monitoring and/or managing device.
<p>Stakeholder 05 – Energy provider 1</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEC deployment, • PV systems deployment, • Bringing renewable systems closer to local people, • NEON consortium member, • PV self-consumption system shared by free with other stakeholders, • Operational and maintenance works, • PV self-consumption system managing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory changes, • Permissions for CEC, • Permissions for renewable energy, • Not predictable electricity price • Reduced return of investment (PV self-consumption) due to free -sharing with the CEC- • Possible extra taxes, • Stakeholders understanding, • CEC legal constitution • Not existing Spanish normative for the CEC.

<p>Stakeholder 06 – End user 5</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Saving money, • Saving energy, • Possible existing individual self-consumption system to be shared with CEC, • Small consumer helping to the CEC growth, • Smart meter for measuring consumed energy. It helps to take decisions about consumption habits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High electricity prices, • Smart meter only shows consumptions. It is not possible to manage loads.
<p>Stakeholder 07 – End user 6</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electricity bill reduction, • Use of renewable energy, • Helping to get a better and sustainable world for living, • Well-known person in Villacañas. It could help for attracting people for joining to the CEC, • Ex-member of the town council. It could help for permissions with local administration due to her internal local process's knowledge. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High electricity prices • Here is not any consumption monitoring and/or managing device.
<p>Stakeholder 08 – Energy provider 2</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renewable energy for charging batteries, • NEON consortium member • Storage system shared by free with other stakeholders, • Operational and maintenance works • Storage system managing, • Storage from PV system surplus, • Available energy for non-solar hours, • Showing PV and storage as a perfect couple. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Batteries management costs, • Normative, • Recycling batteries, • Batteries lifetime.
<p>Stakeholder 09 – End user 7</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Showing people about e-mobility benefits, • Electric cars number growth, • Electricity bill reduction, • Key actor for EV market boost, • Important consumer in the CEC, • Energy and money saving. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High electricity prices, • Reduced number of electric vehicles, • Not concordance between energy consumed and provided to EV (from electricity bills energy consumed and payment platform for owners of electric cars), • Not existing device for monitoring.

<p>Stakeholder 10 – End user 8</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of mobility costs • Energy for recharging EV • Regular consumer (EV recharging service). • Small portable recharging device for electric vehicles, • APP available for energy needs knowledge. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possible EV recharging station damage, • Reduced number of public EV recharging station,
<p>Stakeholder 11 – Energy provider 3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More electric vehicles, • Boosting e-mobility, • Other services existing (LPG refuelling), • Contacting with many owners of electric vehicles who are already using the EV recharging station (attracting end user to the CEC), • Internet connection available. • Unique EV recharging station in Villacañas (at medium charging speed), • EV recharging station shared by free with other stakeholders, • Operational and maintenance works, • EV recharging station managing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Permissions need (grid company, administration), • General costs, • Lower investment profit due to free sharing of EV recharging station, • Not enough number of electric cars • It is needed an external company (Electromaps) for managing the payment platform, • Differencing users of EV recharging station depending on if they are integrated in the CEC or not.

Table 9 CEC04 interview results table

If we analyse last table, we can extract some conclusions from the stakeholders' answers during the interviews. There are some similarities in general, and from either energy providers or end users' point of view. All these conclusions can be summarized in the following table.

End users' general point of view.	Needs:	Pains:
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of electricity prices • Reduction of mobility costs. • Growth of EV recharging stations number. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High electricity prices. • Rising electricity prices tendency. • New mode. Uncertainly behaviour. • Not concordance between energy purchased and energy consumed.
	Opportunities:	Difficulties:
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy and money savings. • Renewable energy uses. • Small consumers together as a big consumer. • Some end users could help to the CEC growth thanks to their relationships in Villacañas. • End users feel comfortable due to close relationship between stakeholders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced number of public EV recharging stations. • Not all end users have a smart meter for consumption monitoring and management.

Energy providers' general point of view.	Needs:	Pains:
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting CEC • Boosting renewable and e-mobility projects. • Growth of Electric cars number. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Permissions • General costs • Lower profit of investment due to free sharing existing energy services • Regulatory changes • Possible damage in EV recharging stations
	Opportunities:	Difficulties:
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing energy service management • Operational and maintenance works. • Bringing renewable energy closer to local people. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not specific normative • Stakeholders understanding • Possible material replacement (infrastructure)

4.4 CEC 04 -STAINS CITY

Based on the assessment performed in T1.1, as part of the Task 1.2 and prepare task 1.3 **Cross-sectoral arrangements and stakeholder interaction**, STAIN CEC main stakeholder has been Identified. Indeed, the objectives of these tasks are to create and implement energy services co-creation process with the stakeholders within each NEON’s CEC.

The figure below displays STAINS City emerging CEC stakeholders mapping related to all the existing services identified, by distinguishing:

- The services core users and the actors that will be significantly impacting the services creation a: ENGIE, INDUSTREET and both offices building occupants (employees, researchers, teacher, trainees)
- The front-end actors within the second circle, considered as direct stakeholders and will be in direct interaction with the services users: ENOGRID, Facility manager, energy provider and Hydrogen Lab-ENGIE CRIGEN.
- and finally, the back-stage actors or within the larger circle who are indirect stakeholders and not in direct interaction with the services users: DSO, assets and properties managers, equipment’s manufacturer, and technical experts.

Figure 6 CEC02-STAINS CITY stakeholders mapping

This stakeholder mapping helped ENGIE as the CEC leader to have a clearer understanding of how the existing energy services identified in T1.1 could affect the core stakeholders and focus on the core actors to prepare the stakeholders interviews as part of the service’s co-creation process activities.

ENGIE has performed two interviews' sessions with INDUSTREET director, IT manager, Maintenance manager and the site manager. The table below summarizes the analysis of the interview results and map the core stakeholders identified opportunities, needs, pain and difficulties.

Stakeholder name and type	Needs, Opportunities	Pains, Difficulties
INDUSTREET Maintenance Manager and IT Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historize the functioning of the systems to better diagnose and optimize the operations, • Perform predictive maintenance and programming on air handling units, • Leverage Industreet Data-Lack project, • Regulate office temperature, • Raise office building (employees and trainees) awareness, • Monitor the building consumption in real time, • establish a monthly dashboard to better manage consumption, • Optimize PV production thanks to weather forecasts, • Create interactions from a business skills point of view, • Share spaces and equipment's with ENGIE. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Go further on the technical level relating to the management of the building with the maintenance service of the heating, water, and power, • Carry out evaluations and energy balances in a regular and automatic way, • Create interactions from a business skills point of view, create links with students, • Know how to share spaces and equipment? • The forecast of the occupation at the level of the building • Improves the energy class of the building estimated "C".
INDUSTREET Director and Site Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share PV energy production locally, • Provide data to assess the production and collective self-consumption potential, • Produce and share local green hydrogen, • Install a hydrogen station and invest potentially in FCEVs (reflections), • Share contacts to promote and expand the community, • Reflect on common subjects such as predictive maintenance, NDT (Non-Destructive Testing). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimize consumption at night, • Optimize equipment management, in particular AHU (Air handling Unit).

The analysis of this interviews allowed to have a better understanding of the needs and the motivation of INDUSTREET by joining and participation in the CEC step-up also raised some **Table 10 CEC04-STAINS CITY interview results table** questions regarding the two core -stakeholder (ENGIE and INDUSTREET) expectations, such as:

- The consideration the occupation status of the of the premises in the optimization of heating / air conditioning / ventilation,
- The technical limitation related to the building and its different assets management,
- The frequency of the weather predictions calculation and their use.

These previous points were considered in the next step of the co-creation process and discussed within the collaborative workshop with the core-stakeholders of STAINS CITY CEC.

5. NEON CECs services co-creation sessions

The task leader has proposed a dedicated protocol to give some support to the use cases leaders.

This protocol gave the key information to carry out the collaborative workshop such as the type of workshop, the duration, the deadline, the required material and tools, the process and recommended timing.

Workshop type	Collaborative workshop In person workshop is highly recommended, otherwise it could be online
Deadline	Before February 28 th
Duration	120 min
Required material	Laptop, webcam (in case of a remote workshop)
Required supports	Survey / list of questions, registration authorization document, Power Point presentation
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome all the participants • Explain the workshop objectives, process, and rules (kindness, listening, participation, volunteering... using a Power Point presentation in line with the project's graphic identity - • Share the interviews results / main insights and give the participants the opportunity to react • Compare the stakeholders' activities, actors, energy uses, pain points and needs • Share the T1.1 results (cross-integrated services) • Co-identify opportunities for the CEC from the previous data (activities, actors, energy uses, pain points and needs • Prioritize these opportunities thanks to an impact-effort matrix • Describe the quick-wins among these opportunities (less effort – more impact) with the Business Model Canva <p>Thank all the participants and recall the next step (NEON next tasks and CEC's construction steps</p>

Table 11 NEON CECs services co-creation sessions protocol

Then we created and proposed two mains' templates:

1. An effort-impact matrix to position all the services opportunities and identify the quick-wins within the NEON project,
2. A complete Business Model Canvas (BMC) to make a business description of these quick wins.

The next sections describe the use cases’ workshops results for each use case.

5.1. CEC 01 -BERCHIDDA co-creation session

On Wednesday 13 April 18:00 – 20:30 GridAbility hosted the NEON project workshop at the Berchidda Wine Museum. The objective of the workshop was to map needs and possible interactions between private users and local companies in the upcoming CEC.

Figure 7 NEON project workshop at the Berchidda Wine Museum.

• Participants profiles

A public invite addressing all Berchidda citizens (3000) has been posted on the official Municipality Website and publicized on the Municipality Facebook page. The invitation posted publicly, open to all Berchidda citizens, was furthermore sent directly to the five participants of the interviews.

14 people were present to the workshop including GridAbility staff, the Mayor and Municipality Townhall representatives.

Number of participants in total	Female 5	Male 9	Total 14
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• Agenda settings

The agenda detailed below was pursued:

- 18:00 – Reception and Registration of participants.
- 18:30 – Welcome: Simona D'Oca.
- 18:40 – Institutional greetings Mayor Berchidda.
- 18:50 – Introduction to the objectives of the workshop.
- 19:00 – Presentation and discussion of results interviews with citizens.
- 19:30 – Presentation and discussion of questionnaire results for citizens.
- 20:00 – Compilation of the Efforts – Benefits matrix.
- 20:30 – Thanks and conclusions.

- **Ideas generation**

An introduction to the NEON project was given at the beginning of the workshop. The event started by introducing the overall concept of Citizen Energy Communities. It was mentioned clearly that, apart from the technological advancements, the social dimension of the energy transition is key, the individual's behaviour matters, and everybody can contribute their part. We then illustrated that the NEON project objective at large is to develop knowledge and tools that can support CECs across Europe, while the workshop goal specifically was to gather their feedback so that the NEON team can better understand and can learn what matters and what they would find most useful in the Berchidda community. It has been mentioned that, in fact, every CEC could have their own goals and ideas on how to create a more sustainable future, and examples for community goals are introduced, such as:

- Save on the cost of energy and maximize the return on investment.
- Achieve energy self-sufficiency for the community.
- Enable freedom of choice to install equipment.

We mentioned that with this workshop we were exquisitely interested in understanding what are the most pressing goals for the Berchidda CEC.

After the introduction, main energy services that will be included in the Berchidda CEC have been presented, including:

- RES penetration with installation of additional Photovoltaic generation systems.
- Retrofit with highly efficient electric heat pumps.
- Batteries energy storage systems.
- Metering and Monitoring through smart meters and an Energy Management Platform.
- Autonomous micro-grids.
- Public EV charging stations.
- Collective PV self-consumption.
- P4P Pay for Performance for share of renewable energy value among CEC's members.

- **Selection and prioritization**

After a general introduction to the project and workshop objectives, we opened a plenary debate focusing on highlighting the actions and necessary steps for the implementation of the CEC and the citizen engagement. The following matrix was compiled in real-time using sticky notes on a table board.

Figure 8 CECO1- Services Impact Effort matrix

- **Opportunities description and initial business plan**

Not all the citizens who replied to the workshop invite, including the ones who have been personally invited by email, attended the workshop. As a matter of fact, we expected at least 20 participants to attend the event, while only few citizens and representatives from the local industries and SMEs were present at the meeting. For this reason, it was not possible to validate in that occasion parts of the initial Business Model Canvas in the planned co-creation process.

However, concerns about the impact of rising energy prices on the price of local products emerged during the workshop. Indeed, local SMEs expressed their interest in conducting energy audits of their factories with R2M Energy in order to decrease their energy needs and costs and keep the price of their products unchanged, so as not to risk compromising their sales.

Another concern that was raised by some citizens was the higher involvement of the Municipality in the investment of renewable energy sources plants to cover the electricity demand of the citizens.

Then, additional in person meetings with the representative of the Municipality and the DSO AEC, and online meetings with partners have been conducted afterwards to discuss further in detail the issue raised during the workshop. Like for the dimensioning of the EV chargers and choice of strategic points where to install them, or to discuss the possible options to install a big, centralized PV plant with national, regional incentives or through other EU projects. Indeed, the Municipality is working on the modernization of its electricity grid to upgrade it to an urban microgrid by deploying and extended number of smart meters,

by renovating its electrical cabin and by building a free communication network that will interconnect all users.

- **Conclusions and perspectives**

In Berchidda, the general atmosphere of the event was relaxed, casual and cooperative. This is due to the fact most of the citizens already know each other at personal (if not familiar) level.

Participants to the workshop appeared generally concerned about surging energy costs, debating about the foreseen increase in their domestic energy bills. This aspect concurred as a **positive driver** for the citizens, municipality, and DSO, who perceived the opportunity, via the formation of the energy community, to become independent from the local energy provider and decrease the risk generated by energy dependency from the national grid.

A representation of the Municipality Townhall, the local DSO together with the mayor attended the event and sat at the discussion tables together with the citizens. This increased the mixite' of the dialogues, the perspectives discussed, enabling internal problem-solving debates that concluded with several clarifications and doubts clearance for the citizens.

A diffuse concern related to the actual benefits of the energy community was expressed by some participants, especially from the ones who already have some PV generation installed and already take advantage from their individual self-consumption. The main pain point is associated to the additional installation costs connected to the new installations and the worry the overall return of investment would not be convenient for the individuals. In this context, the exploitation of local, national, or even EU-level incentives for the coverage of new installation was proposed from the citizens as possible solution to overcome the economic exposure and make the energy community sustainable and profitable.

Overall, we found a low level of citizen's engagement to the event. Not all the citizens who replied to the workshop invite, including the ones who have been personally invited by email, attended the workshop. As a matter of fact, we expected at least 20 participants to attend the event, while only few citizens and representatives from the local industries and SMEs were present at the meeting. Therefore, one immediate next step will be to improve the engagement strategy plan to increase the number of citizens reached, to address better the wants and needs of the citizens to attract their attention, and finally improve the disseminating material (presentations during events, brochures/flyers/posters, ...) and the communication of the objectives and benefits that the project can bring to them in a more understandable and attractive way.

In parallel, Gridability and R2M Energy will keep focusing on the deployment of the energy services identified for the pilot:

- Technical and legal assistance to the Municipality for the formalization of Berchidda CEC (supported by Energy4Com) and for the modernization of its electric grid with the installation of smart meters for the metering and monitoring management, of additional RES plants to increase production of energy from renewables and of centralized energy storage systems to optimize the management of the distributed energy sources of the city.
- Social/Technical assistance to the citizens to in one hand answers to their rising fears of energy prices, and on the other hand to raise their energy awareness and engagement, and to teach them the optimal behaviors to adopt in order to reduce their consumptions already from the demand side.

- Energy audits in community's buildings and deployment of highly efficient heat pumps in around 10 to 15 households to improve their energy performances and reduce their energy expenses.
- EV charging service that will add value to the city, further promote tourism (by making Berchidda a strategic intermediate point of recharge for tourist with EV between the two main areas of tourism of North Sardinia).
- Collective PV self-consumption to increase energy sharing of locally produced energy from renewables among the members of the community to reduce the overall city's demand from fossil fuels produced energy (reduce carbon footprint) and enhance 100% energy independency of the city and 100% coverage from renewables. At building level, it will reduce the energy expenses of the single prosumers and more importantly at community level it will reduce the overall energy demand from the national grid and the hourly self-consumed energy will be valued by the national incentive to repay the initial investment to upgrade the system and move towards the energy transition from fossil fuel to renewable sources.
- Peak shaving and load shifting through residential battery energy storage systems (at the moment of writing around 20 systems of 5.1kWh storage in 20 households) and bigger centralized energy storage systems.
- Pay for Performance to allow prosumers of the community to share their energy surplus within the community and increase the total share of self-consumed energy at community level that is economically valued by the Italian incentive.

5.2. CEC02 -DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE co-creation session

Figure 9 Domaine de la source – DDLS - (Sept 2021)

Participants profiles

- NEON Albedo manager
- NEON Albedo research director
- Stakeholder 1: retired engineer, owner, DDLS committee
- Stakeholder 2: retired professor, owner, DDLS committee
- Stakeholder 3: retired, owner, DDLS committee
- Stakeholder 4: owner, DDLS committee
- Stakeholder 5: Condominium agent manager
- **Agenda settings**

Workshop type	Collaborative workshop In person workshop is highly recommended, otherwise it could be online
Date	July 21 – Sept 21 – Oct 21 -> April 22 (phone calls)
Duration	4h in July and sept 21
Required material	Laptop, paper, and pencils
Written supports	Energy draft analysis done by DDLS people
Process and timing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome all the participants (5 min)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain the Neon project within energy actual frame (60 min) • DDLS explain the energy model of the building (60 min) • Discussion to extract actual and future pains and needs (45 min) • Co-identify opportunities for DDLS vs Neon Project (15 min) • Detailed visit of the technical room (20 min) • Thank all the participants and conclusion (5 min)
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Table 12 CEC02- stakeholders collaborative workshop agenda

• **Ideas generation**

First meeting (July 21) 3h: presentation of teams and Neon project.
 Technical visit of the energy installations – collect of data

Figure 10 CEC03 boiler room and smart meters

In the first picture we have an overview of boiler room and below are some counters for hot domestic water and solar power plant.

Second meeting (Sept 21) 6-7h: technical visit and cocreation meeting:

- DDLS expectations,

- Presentation of what is an energy community and the French regulation about it. During this presentation people were curious and interested, this is due to their technical and scientific background,
- Understand the problem.

As DDLS has a complex energy flow (schema below) and the main question is how to optimize both:

- flows of energy?
- energy systems efficiency?
- energy usage efficiency?
- energy production flow?

Figure 11 Actual energy flow of DDLS

The main topic that appears was the need to synchronize solar energy production with an acceptable usage.

In other words, in DDLS, in a collective engagement way how can I change my behaviour in order to reduce energy demand?

And is energy community size influence global efficiency of energy usage?

If I extend the community with other buildings around, does it influence in a positive or negative manner regarding optimization objectives?

Another question that appears was: in which terms do we want to optimize, Economic, environmental, or consumption aspect?

Once the problem has been underlined the question was how to do this, what is the methodology, does it exist on the shelf?

At the end emerge the question of French regulation regarding CEC.

if we want to summarize with a drawing, the problem could be the following:

Figure 12 : brain storming board - Synthesis design of DDLS actual and future needs

Of course, behind this flow, there is also the uncertainty of French energy regulation evolution. Renewable energies generate instability on the grid and self-consumption is encourage because it reduces this impact. Another problem: it is impossible to understand an energy flow diagram using only the annual or monthly consumption; To do a correct analysis of energy demand relative to produced energy, we need to have at least an hourly power timestamp. And as these energy flows are constantly changing, the optimization decision support system should be done in real time. We have also to consider the storage capacity of domestic hot water or future electric vehicles or even occupants discomfort capability acceptance.

During the coworking session, thanks crossing different point of view and experiences, it has emerged these main ideas:

1. We should create a sort of dynamic audit to cross the different flows of both energy production, storage, consumption allowing us to help in the decision.
2. We can inform people when the best moment is to consume energy
3. Having a measurement of the flows allow us to better understand the way to optimize
4. Having a clear vision of prices and systems yields could help to take decisions
5. We could ask other buildings around to setup an energy community

• Selection and prioritization

In the effort impact matrix analysis, we have introduced another parameter: scalability. By example installing IOT sensors in large numbers of flats require a lot of efforts of installation, the scalability is very low. In comparison developing algorithms to load data coming from smart meters already installed also require a lot of effort in IT development but has a very high scalability. In this way we have rate the ideas under these criteria: effort, impact but also thinking scalability

Understanding the ideas that emerge within the analysis session, we have finally grouped the ideas in three mains business:

- Power to Grid 100% SELF-CONSUMPTION in an extended community: The economic model of selling energy push to try to have the maximum of self-consumption. It is very likely that the extension of the community to other buildings will allow an increase in self-consumption performance.
- Energy efficiency: Improving systems efficiency will allow to maximize the value of renewable energy production. In fact, traditional building energy systems are designed without integrating self-consumption. Improving existing energy systems means to integrate in a deeper way energy systems and solar power plant and usage of energy.
- Sobriety: Helping people to better use energy is a real service of a CEC. Behavior's change is part of energy community's success. This needs to integrate self-consumption, flexibility, and sobriety in the usage of energy.

The rating of the above services has been done by experience and are more relative between all than absolute evaluation.

The graphic below represents the different actions regarding impact on economic point of view for energy consumption. We can see that 100% SELF-CONSUMPTION; EXTENDED COMMUNITY are the lower effort tasks with the maximum impact.

Figure 13 Impact matrix in DDLS

Dynamic audit has not a big impact but is mandatory to understand better energy systems.

• **Opportunities description and initial business plan**

100% Self consumption service has the goal to maximize the local energy consumption while reducing a large part of energy consumption from the grid. This service needs the right design to synchronize Solar power plant and usage needs while the usage level requires to help occupants to decide when the right moment is to consume energy.

This service requires solar powerplant design skill, building energy knowledge and sociological skill to help customers behaviour’s change.

Mainly social building owner are interested in this service, but also solar power plant installer could be interested to bring a new service for customers.

Obtaining 100% self-consumption means:

- Extended community
- All the solar production is consumed on site
- To adapt energy systems, demand with solar cycle
- To adapt stakeholder behaviour with solar production

- To setup DR mechanism
- To validate this economic model

Extended community came as evidence after we explain the cycle of consumption of different building types. As the participants are aware of energy it was really easy to convince them that extending the community all around in Villard de Lans could be an opportunity to develop an energy mix which optimize the global building efficiency and also to disseminate the self-consumption process.

The question that remains is: How efficiency will be improve in an extended community?

Again, mathematics will be a suitable way to optimize the community.

Efficiency: Energy systems are the key of DDLS. All energy needs (Heating, DHW) are produced with electricity (Boilers and heat pump). Managing in a better way the set of boilers, Heat Pump and hot water tank storage is a way to save energy consumption. This will need ESCO skills but also mathematics to optimize the storage with the solar production cycle.

We have already started expertise of the energy systems; the possible gains are around 20% for DHW production and usage. We will need to add extra sensors and measurements in the heating room.

Sobriety service: create a link between people's energy usage and energy production. This will be done by the use of an external software. We are analysing existing solutions on the market. The expected impact will have to be followed during the 2 first years at least.

• Conclusions and perspectives

In Domaine de la Source we have the chance to experiment energy community development. For sure this development requires both building energy expertise and IT development.

But this pilot is a wonderful testing platform to develop a building and extended community in a small town. Probably we must extend our promotion to major of the city of Villar de Lans.

The next step will be:

- Energy flow deep analysis and eventual extended measurement
- Energy community business analysis
- Energy community law feasibility

The main goal of Domaine De La Source CEC is to improve energy efficiency, this will be done in DDLS with influence stakeholders' behaviour, increase the management (the synchronisation) of solar energy production and systems consumption. These are the way we will follow in the next tasks of Neon Project.

It is impossible to detail more all these topics (benefits, costs etc...) before having done the actual CEC feasibility analysis.

5.3. CEC03 - POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS co-creation session

According to NEON project schedule and planification for Task T1.2, on Tuesday 19th April 2022, GFM carried out the collaborative workshop with several future stakeholders, both energy providers and end users.

It was performed in GFM headquarters, where all existing services (EV Charging point, PV power plant and energy storage system) are installed and working. The objective of the workshop was explaining the CEC model proposed by GFM as business model based on an energy and money savings virtual balance.

The three existing services were shown to some end users and some ideas were given by end users to improve the initial proposal given by GFM.

Figure 14 CEC03-Services co-creation workshop

- **Participants profiles**

A total of eight people were present during the workshop. Two of them participated as both energy provider and end user. The participant profiles are summarized in the following table:

ATTENDING LIST

Name	Stakeholder mode (End User / Energy Provider)
Stakeholder 1	End user / Energy provider
Stakeholder 2	End user
Stakeholder 3	End user
Stakeholder 4	End user
Stakeholder 5	End user
Stakeholder 6	End user / Energy provider
Stakeholder 7	End user
Stakeholder 8	End user

Table 13 CEC03 services co-creation workshop participants list

- **Agenda settings**

Date: 19th April 2022

AGENDA

16.00 H – RECEPTION.

16.15 H - WELCOME.

16.30 H – WHAT IS NEON?

16.40 H – WHAT IS AN ENERGY COMMUNITY? WHICH IS THE ORIGIN?

16.50 H – WHAT IS EXPECTED THANK TO NEON?

17.00 H – PARTICIPANT LIST IN NEON PROJECT.

17.10 H – OBJECTIVE OF WORKSHOP.

17.20 H – DIFFERENT PILOTS IN NEON.

17.30 H – COFFEE BREAK.

18.00 H – PREVIOUS STEPS IN NEON. TASK T1.1.

18.15 H – EXISTING ENERGY SERVICES DESCRIPTION.

18.45 H – IDEA FOR ENERGY COMMUNITY FOR CITIZENS IN SPANISH PILOT.

19.30 H – SKATEHOLDERS INTERVIEWS RESULTS.

20.00 H – IMPACT EFFORT MATRIX.

20.15 H – BMC (QUICK WIN OPPORTUNITIES).

20.30 H – SKATEHOLDERS PROPOSALS? BRAINSTORMING? NEW OPPORTUNITIES?

21.30 H – END OF WORKSHOP.

- **Ideas generation**

The workshop was focus on explaining about the general concepts the future CEC would consist of. The main idea is to implement a system based on a virtual energy balance between stakeholders, both energy providers and end users.

It was explained how this system would seek to dynamically distribute the available energy in real time according to the consumption of each of the members of the CEC. In case there is a surplus available, it would be used to be stored to cover peaks of high demand or periods of no solar production.

With this community model, an attempt was made to explain not only the possible economic savings, but also the environmental advantages. It was also explained the benefit for the community of efficiency from the point of view of consumption, where it is intended that the energy is consumed at the time it is generated, eliminating at such times, the dependence on external energy of the community.

During the previous interviews, it was detected a certain suspicion about new business models related to energy. Many regulatory changes have been carried out by several governments (mainly about renewable systems). That was the main reason why GFM (Spanish pilot leader and member of NEON consortium) perceived that one defined model should be given to stakeholders to avoid them feeling scared about CECs. The presentation and explanation of the model presented at the meeting aroused curiosity in many of the attendees, which also generated a number of questions that helped those less familiar with the technical aspects of an energy community to better understand it.

It should be noted that GFM is a well-known company in the sector, especially in the central part of the Iberian Peninsula. In Villacañas, the village where the pilot project will be carried out, the company is well known by all the neighbours, and this, together with the proximity to the people, helped to ensure that the ideas put forward at the meeting were well received by the participants. This ultimately creates a favourable situation for users to become part of the energy community. GFM also has relationships with different companies in the sector as well as service providers and energy suppliers, which is understood to be important to have the right basis for the development of a community.

Related to the CEC implementation in the daily lifes of each CEC potential member, one of the most important aspects was to do something easy for them. Stakeholders should not do any effort to enjoy the CEC advantages (Only if not available, they will require the installation and configuration of measuring equipment.). In addition to it, if some efficient habits are detected or if consumption tendence is decreasing, some extra benefits could be assigned to those stakeholders (This will be defined as Pay4performance contracts in future deliverables.).

According to end users' feedback, GFM realised two main aspects should be taken into consideration with the same importance: environmentally sustainable solutions deployment and economical aspects (as a saving tool). It should be noted that the main attraction for members of this community is the advantage of better energy prices, given the inflation in energy prices that has been seen over the last few years.

Figure 15 CEC 03 Stakeholders interaction schema

A simple scheme about the interaction between stakeholder is shown.

As it could be seen in this proposed model, it may be needed an intelligent exchange energy platform. It would measure all the consumptions from the end users and all the energy provided by the existing services. Using this information, a virtual energy and money balance could be carried out. It will depend on end users' consumption curve.

Every stakeholder will have their own contract with the grid company. In Spain, there is a very fix model related to electricity market. Thanks to an internal agreement, every stakeholder can compensate between themselves with the aim of achieving a net energy and money goals.

This solution proposed to stakeholder is a complementary model, working in parallel with their existing contracts with the grid company.

In this way the main objectives in this CEC will be:

- Using renewable energy system (when the energy is produced if its possible).
- Boosting e-mobility.
- Showing storage systems as a perfect couple for renewable systems.
- Efficient habits of consumption and driving achievement.
- Reducing electricity dependence
- Reducing energy and mobility costs
- Simple system which is easy for replication.

The three existing energy services for Spanish pilot are placed in GFM headquarters. They are shared by GFM as a NEON project consortium member:

LOCATION: CALLE LAS CABEZAS 16.
45860 VILLACAÑAS (TOLEDO - SPAIN)

The existing energy services are described below:

- 1- PV Self consumption system (Service provider: GFM) This service will be in charge of generating the photovoltaic energy to be consumed in the energy community. This energy can be consumed directly at the time of generation, both by end-consumers and other service providers, as well as stored for later use.

DESCRIPTION PV SYSTEM

- 32.08 kWp (Bifacial Mono PERC + Polycrystalline)
- 33.5 kWn PV inverters (Fronius SYMO 10 kW (1) + Fronius PRIMO GEN 24 5 kW (3) + Fronius PRIMO 5 kW (1) + Fronius PRIMO 3.5 kW(1))

OWNER:

- GFM

- 2- EV recharging station (Service provider: GFMCA) This service will be available to the public, both for members of the community and external users, so that it can be used as a service for the internal financing of the community as well as for the promotion of the community.

DESCRIPTION STORAGE SYSTEM

- INGECON RAPID TRIO EV RECHARGING STATION (INGETEAM). 50 kW DC (CHADEMO & CCS) + 40 kW AC (MENNEKES)

OWNER:

- GFMCA

- 3- Storage system (Service provider: GFM) This service is perhaps the most important for the community, as it will be responsible for providing greater flexibility to the system, giving the possibility of

consuming energy in periods of non-generation, thus helping to increase the efficiency of the system (if we understand efficiency as energy consumed vs. energy produced).

DESCRIPTION STORAGE SYSTEM
 - 2000AH LEAD ACID BATTERIES. 48V
 - Inverters/Charger Victron Multiplus 48/5000/70

OWNER:
 - GFM

Just connected to the three existing services there are some end users enjoying the energy provided. It will be promoted that the energy is consumed at the moment it is generated or, failing that, stored, trying to avoid, as far as possible, consuming energy from the grid or feed-in the excess of energy generated. In other words, the main interest of the whole CEC is to minimize the energy produced not used or stored.

CURRENT END USERS / STAKEHOLDERS FOR ENERGY COMMUNITY

PILOT LOCATION: CALLE LAS CABEZAS 16. 45860 VILLACAÑAS (TOLEDO - SPAIN)

Thanks to this model, one end user could take advantage of existing energy services despite not being directly connected or having their own PV installation. So, it could be possible to attract more end users living in Villacañas (on the other part of the city) or even living in closer villages.

- **Selection and prioritization**

After analysing all the stakeholders' profiles (both energy providers and end users) the following impact-effort matrix was defined.

Figure 16 CEC03 services Impact effort matrix

This pilot has a very important advantage. The existing energy services infrastructure freely available by GFM (as NEON project member). It helps very much to the integration in the CEC. All permissions, installation works, commissioning, etc. are done, so they are not necessary for this pilot.

It reduces very much initial costs. That is the reason for the good position of PV self-consumption and storage systems in the impact effort matrix. There is not any effort for end users because they do not have to do anything for enjoying energy from these two existing services once the CEC is working. And they have a strong impact because most of end users are electrical consumers.

On the other hand, the EV recharging station is in worse position. Despite this service is also shared by free for NEON project, there are not many EV cars' owners, so the impact is not very big. In addition to it, for using the energy provided by the station electric cars are needed and it would involve many people buying this kind of cart. In this way an important investment should be carried out by end users, and it is considered a high effort.

On the other hand, if we evaluate the EV charger in terms of efficiency with the rest of the consumers and services in the community, it may be the least efficient service. These services, in general, will be large consumers of energy in short periods of time, which will make them have a great power demander, this,

together with the particular needs of each user, will make their integration a challenge and also probably the less efficient service.

- **Opportunities description and initial business plan**

As it has been mentioned before, the CEC for the Spanish pilot has three existing energy services which are already working for GFM. Once the collaborative workshop was performed, each of them were analysed one by one thoroughly. In this way, some additional opportunities and complementary business models were identified.

All the conclusions have been summarized in ANNEX 02, where the BMC can be studied accordingly.

In the following section these new and additional opportunities for each existing energy service are described.

PV SELF-CONSUMPTION SYSTEMS

- PV plants promotion
- Monitoring and management platform development.
- PV modules and inverters fabrication, installation, configuration (engineering works)
- Marketing publications (newsletters, dissemination)
- Legalization works.
- Reduction of energy consumption based on fossil fuels. (Social opportunities)

ENERGY STORAGE

- Storage plants promotion. (Give visibility to the flexibility it brings to the system.)
- Monitoring and management platform development.
- Batteries and inverter/chargers' fabrication, installation, configuration (engineering works)
- Marketing publications (newsletters, dissemination)
- Legalization works.

EV RECHARGING STATION

- Public EV recharging station promotion
- Monitoring and management platform development.
- EV recharging station fabrication, installation, configuration (engineering works)
- Marketing publications (newsletters, dissemination)
- Legalization works.
- Payment platform developers
- Electric vehicles selling.

Because of CECs, the promotion of these kind of projects is a very good chance for developing new systems and solutions, based on renewable energy and electrical-mobility (from now on, E-mobility) systems, which could be economically financed by small stakeholders, all together. In addition to it, if they work as a group external finance could be got. They can be seen as an important group of consumers by the grid company, and it could involve better conditions for them.

It may happen that some people could not have access to these kinds of services if they were thinking about undertaking an investment for renewable, storage or E-mobility by their own. They could not have money enough. In this way, if several stakeholder finance together a project, it could be easier for them.

In addition to it, CECs is a perfect tool for achieving the decarbonization objectives due to environmentally sustainable solutions using. Renewable systems and E-mobility are essential on the current strategies of several countries in Europe.

All the value chain, associated to each energy service can take advantage of this opportunity (O&M, equipment manufacturers, energy service companies, engineering, etc.)

• Conclusions and perspectives

After the co-creation process the perspectives are good. Stakeholders are decided to create the CEC based on the model previously explained. The idea of GFM being the coordinator of the CEC make them feel comfortable due to its well-known reputation in Villacañas (small location where everyone knows each other).

The two main items, money saving tool and environmentally solutions, are expected to be solved according to this model.

Another interesting point for stakeholders has been the little effort involved from their side within the whole process described above.

Some good ideas were given by stakeholders during the workshop, as extra benefits in the CEC if they get a higher efficiency or if they reduce their consumption.

As efficiency, both for the whole of the model presented in the community, and to individually evaluate each consumer, two main factors are established to consider:

1. The first factor to consider is reducing as much as possible the total energy consumed outside the CEC generation, to ensure that the CEC is as self-sufficient as possible.
2. The second factor, and also related with the previous one is to promote the consumption during de generation hours in order to minimize the energy feed-in the grid which at the end will have a residual value compared with the directly consumed energy.

Those key factors will be the reference to measure the efficiency of the CEC, considering the most efficiency scenario where there is no excess of energy generated and everything is consumed (or stored to be consumed later), the energy consumed (kWh/day) and the energy generated (kWh/day) are perfectly balanced without any unused energy during each specific day.

Next steps are focused on the intelligent exchange platform development, defining the internal agreement for stakeholders and the CEC legally constitution.

From GFM's point of view, if the main goals are achieved, this CEC model would be an example for making possible a quick growth of CEC in Spain. The aim is demonstration the pilot services for replicating in new CECs, make it a reference for energy efficiency and promoting a more sustainable consumption model. If the model is viable, it can be used as a reference for the creation of new communities in other areas around Europe(taking into account the regulations in each country or region).

There are some pains based on a non-flexible energetic Spanish regulation at this moment. It is expected a specific regulation for CECs in the future but for sure this will not become a reality if CECs do not take a place in the energy consumptions models scenario.

All the possible energy services based on renewable (PV, wind, storage, etc) and E-mobility systems will help to decarbonization strategies not only during the use of that energy, also with the generation source and how and when the energy is consumed, which is definitely key piece for greater sustainability in any of the aspects of our daily life

5.4. CEC 04 -STAINS CITY co-creation session

To progress and move further in the NEON service’s co-creation process set-up, on 11th and 15th, April 2022, ENGIE organized a hybrid collaborative workshop session with INDUSTREET. The figure below presents the collaborative board that have been used during these workshops.

Figure 17 STAINS CITY CEC hybrid workshop collaborative board.

Based on the first inventory of the existing energy services and the analysis of the interviews with community core- stakeholders, the objective of this workshop was to co-identify, prioritize, and specify the services that can create value, generate savings in terms of costs and in terms of environmental impact to STAINS CITY CEC. These services could affect both resources and the usage of energy within the STAINS CITY Citizen Community.

- **Participants profiles**

The co-creation workshop that has been experienced at Stains city brought together diverse and complementary profiles:

- Site manager
- IT manager
- Multi-service maintenance manager
- ACP / LEC developer
- Data project manager
- Head of computer science & artificial intelligence Lab
- Service designer

- **Agenda settings**

As a reminder, the main goals of this collaborative sessions were to:

- Share the results of upstream work carried out as part of the NEON project (T1.1 – description of existing services + T1.2 – use cases stakeholders' interviews).
- Go further in the process of co-creating service opportunities for the CEC.
- Use collective intelligence to work on existing ideas and bring them to light new ones.
- Identify opportunities likely to be implemented within the framework of NEON.
- Describe these quick wins from a business point of view to start.

The workshop agenda was:

- Presentation of the work already carried out within the framework of task 1.1 of the NEON project: description of the existing services through their "value statement" and a simplified "BMC".
- Sharing the results of the stakeholder interviews carried out as part of the co-creation process for task 1.2 of the NEON project.
- Discussion based on these data and identification of opportunities for the CEC => collective brainstorming.
- Prioritization of these opportunities thanks to an "impact-effort" matrix => individual positioning then collective discussion then individual vote.
- Focus on quick-wins type opportunities and description via a complete BMC => Collective Business Model Canvas(es).

We also share few rules for the smooth running of the session:

Participation

Listening

Benevolence

Timing respect

- **Ideas generation**

This capture shows the result of the ideation work carried out during the session based on information from the description of the existing services and the interviews. Each participant added post-its with comments, details, ideas based on the services offered by the stakeholders and on the needs, difficulties and pains raised during the interviews.

Figure 18 CEC04 - collaborative's workshop brainstorming board

Then we discussed together each of the emerging clusters and their interdependencies or relationships to bring out common opportunities.

Throughout the discussions (in this ideation phase), the core-stakeholder of STAINS CEC has identified new opportunities, notably, the possibility of exploiting the CEC building consumption and production data (used for R&D project and training) and of extracting the curves and KPIS from real data sets.

The building occupancy was one of the focus topics. It has been highlighted the necessity of the service on the one hand to be able to anticipate the presence in the building and prepare the building areas to have the desired temperature at the arrival of the building's occupants, and on the other hand to ensure the security and safety of the personness present in premises in some cases (e.g.an urgent evacuation).

To optimize the PV production, a nowcast solar service being developed by ENGIE CSAI lab has been briefly discussed. This service tracks the cloud movements in real-time to optimize the PV production, but it has been agreed that this service could be implemented at INDUSTREET premises for research purposes only because the PV production on their rooftop is limited by the DSO and there is not much to do to optimize it.

The predictive maintenance was a topic which the stakeholders were interested to develop. INDUSTREET to maintain the AHU (air handling units) and ENGIE to test PV panels infra-red analysis using the drones.

The common services that both stakeholders have identified and expressed their strong interest to integrate them were the collective self- consumption and the green hydrogen production. They also showed an interest on non-technical services, such as: sharing assets, sharing spaces, plan demonstrators and training session by energy expert and implementing end-users' engagement strategies.

- **Selection and prioritization**

Each participant was then asked to position these opportunities on an impact-effort matrix. After discussing the positions chosen, we voted for the quick-wins type opportunities to be described and specified as a priority within the framework of the project.

Figure 19 CEC04 Services Impact Effort matrix

After the services mapping, two services were identified as a priority by the CEC stakeholders: (1) the Collective self-consumption and (2) the Production and the storage of hydrogen(blue). The advantage of those two services is that the technologies infrastructure is already set out; INDUSTREET owns a PV installation and already producing energy for their premises self-consumption and ENGIE possess a P2G (poser to gas) chain to produce and store hydrogen.

The HVAC optimization service (orange) is important to provide flexibility and to optimize the building consumption behavior. However, to implement this service, an integration of the BMS (building management system) and a set-up of a communication infrastructure is necessary. Due to the non-negligeable efforts and the new investments needed for this BMS integration, this service will not be integrated during the NEON project lifetime but will be considered within STAINS CITY CEC services.

As for the (3) EV charging from clean resources, (4) predictive maintenance, and (5) occupancy prediction (red)services, the stakeholders are confident about their relevance and added value and identified them as possible solutions to expand STAIN CITY CEC and its service offers.

- **Opportunities description and initial business plan**

As described in NEON Grant agreement, CEC STAINS CITY is composed of two sites, both are offices buildings:

- **INDUSTREET:** An innovative training campus on the energy professions and trades of tomorrow. Its own PV production 186 KWC installed on the roof. Regarding production and storage of hydrogen, INDUSTREET is interested in, and they believe it could be developed for mobility and infrastructure.
- **ENGIE CRIGEN building:** ENGIE Corp. Research Center, working on innovation in the different vectors of energy and develop and own hydrogen technologies.

As defined and agreed with the CEC stakeholders, STAIN City will be engaged in setting up two main services: (1) collective-self- consumption and (2) energy compensation by hydrogen production and storage. Once the first session of the collaborative workshop was performed, the second session was dedicated to describing those services from a business point of view using the BMC (Business Model Caneva). Altogether, ENGIE and INDUSTREET described four energy services: **collective self-consumption, Energy electricity compensation with H2 storage during the off PV production period, HVAC system optimization and control, EV charging from clean resources** ANNEX 02 of the present document.

The initial evaluations based on the exploitation of the self-consumption and INDUSTREET PV production, estimated an available PV surplus of between 1 and 4 MWh in the winter period and up to 12 MWh in the summer period.

This energy will be shared with ENGIE to produce green Hydrogen with a P2G system recently purchased by ENGIE CRIGEN.

The energy sharing will enable STAINS CITY CEC members to benefit, on one hand, from renewable energy (as it will be used it according to their needs during off PV production period e.g., at night, and on the other hand, it will allow them to better manage their energy consumption and to generate saving. Savings will be generated by re-invoicing between members based on the PV production and Hydrogen production or by selling the remaining surplus (after self-consumption within the CEC) to the balance manager.

All the details and the business description of the services are shared in ANNEX 02.

- **Conclusions and perspectives**

In conclusion, we have identified several opportunities in various domains. Although some ideas are very relevant for the proper functioning and dynamism of the future CEC, they are out of NEON project scope because of time limits (some ideas require significant technical and human efforts and cannot be specified in the project times). We will thus focus on the opportunities that correspond not only to the NEON project expectations, but also which can be achieved within the project timeline.

The pilot CEC STAINS City will therefore focus on the following objectives:

- Compensate electricity and thermal consumption of the demo by the local Production (PV)
- Produce H2 from the PV panels, store it and use it thanks to the fuel cells.
- The hybrid heat pumps installed for heating and cooling of the offices, will be exploited to provide the flexibility for improved grid operation.
- If the parking space owner joins the community, green sources (PV and H2) will be considered for provision of electricity for recharging 2 EV station.

The aim of energy efficiency services defined by ENGIE and Idustreet is not necessarily to improve the intrinsic energy efficiency of the office complex buildings (the case with building renovation for example), but rather to have better overall energy performance, which can therefore go through better management of the energy assets, systems, and the use of local energy to consume less from the main grid (therefore PV self-consumption services, and production of green H2).

In the case of CEC STAINS CITY, some energy efficiency services (such as renovation) do not make sense since the office complex has been constructed in 2020 respecting the latest norms and regulations. So, the energy efficiency services will be reached through: 1)- self-consumption to reduce the energy consumed from the main grid and promote consumption from clean and sustainable resources, 2)- manage more efficiently the building energy assets, and 3)- improve the building HVAC load profile.

Conclusions

The actions carried out in Task 1.2 framework were aimed at laying foundations for NEON services design in the lifetime of the NEON project. The goal was to describe the co-ideated services from a business model perspective. This deliverable is based on the outcome of the co-creation process (interviews and a collaborative workshop with stakeholders) conducted in the four pilot areas, reflecting the mutual agreement on effective service offer for energy efficiency and flexibility exploitation, as well as on the leveraging service concepts to enable cross-service integration, and deliver optimal energy assets scheduling and building control.

The overall target of this work was to design the field work and elaborate an approach for end-users' engagement to understand their needs, motivations, energy practices, and better design services.

Co-creation is a collaborative practice that gives the ability to collectively produce a shared vision of things and to co-develop new value, the core of NEON project. As anticipated, the general steps were:

1. Engagement of the CECs' stakeholders
2. Understanding their needs and consolidating collected data
3. A collaborative phase to brainstorm and ideate new solutions to meet stakeholder needs and pains
4. Bringing together data and ideas and define priority solutions
5. Testing solutions and validating them with respect to initial needs
6. Taking measurement of efficiency in each CEC and how the measurement is realized.

This actual co-creation process was based on three macro steps:

- 1st macro-step → Planning
- 2nd macro-step → Individual interviews
- 3rd macro-step → Collaborative workshop

Moreover, the main results emerged by the process and exposed below represent the foundation for cross-sectoral arrangements and stakeholder interaction (Task 1.3), for matching innovative services and CEC requirements (Task 1.4) as well as for designing the NEON platform design identify actual KPIs (Task 1.5). The results from the service offer co-creation and business planning presented in this report will be crucial for the definition of multi-actor energy performance contracting models and guidelines (Task 2.2) and the specification of financial structures and service facilitators involvement (Task 2.3).

The main conclusions that emerged for the pilot areas are briefly summarized here. In Berchidda the surging energy costs were identified as a driver to create the energy community that could leverage energy independence while, on the other hand, there were some concerns related to the benefit of the community. In Domaine de la Source, next steps for techno-economic and legal analysis were identified, as well as the needs related to buildings and IT expertise. In Polígono industrial De Las Cabezas two opportunities with high impact and low effort were identified: PV self-consumption and storage systems. Finally, Stains City highlighted the complex nature of CECs, which in some aspects requires significant technical and human efforts difficult to reach within the timescales of the NEON project.

A summary focus is then proposed for each pilot CEC.

BERCHIDDA

Involved stakeholders perceived the arising opportunities regarding an empowerment of an Energy Community to face and mitigate the effect of surging energy costs and linked increase in their domestic energy bills. The formation of the energy community was considered crucial to become independent from the local energy provider and lower the risk generated by energy dependency from the national grid. A rare point in Berchidda's favour is that it owns its own electricity grid, which is uncommon in Italy and therefore allows it to escape some of the limitations of Italian energy services legislation. Indeed, it can have full direct control of feed-in flows in order to favour the use of locally produced energy from renewables and thus not limit itself to the benefit of the individual end-user/prosumer operating in self-consumption but can aim for 100 per cent energy independence of the city by optimising the sharing of energy produced by prosumers among its citizens. To do so, the Municipality is working on finding funds and dimensioning of a first 50kWh centralised battery storage system (4 are envisioned for a total of 200kWh) to optimise the smart management of its distributed energy sources and of additional centralised RES.

Given the main concerns NEON could play a crucial role reducing potential additional installation costs connected to the new installations and guaranteeing an overall return of investment to generate an advantage to CEC's members. In addition, the exploitation of local, national, or even EU-level incentives for the coverage of new installation may be a possible solution to innovate the electricity infrastructures, overcome the economic exposure and make the energy community sustainable and profitable.

Increasing the awareness and the commitment of citizens represents the main challenge for Berchidda pilot, in order to effectively implement the objectives defined in the co-creation process. A greater citizens' involvement in this process would also bring benefits from a social point of view, also since Berchidda is a small municipality where people know each other well. An engagement and recruitment strategy plan is being developed with the Municipality to increase the information on the NEON project on the official website of the Municipality, pop up messages are being sent through telegram and different social media channels, and in person meetings are planned in the next months to enhance more discussions with the citizens that asked to energy retrofit their homes to lower their bills.

DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE

Domaine de la Source represents a great chance to experiment energy community development if the pilot area will be able to increase building energy expertise and IT development. The co-creation process offered the nudge to extend NEON promotion to major of the city of Villar de Lans.

The co-creation process resulted in the identification of three mains businesses: 100% self-consumption, pushed by the economic model of selling energy; extended community, because it is very likely that the extension of the community to other buildings will allow an increase in self-consumption performance (scalability); dynamic audit, to improve energy flows between the various consumers.

According to the results of stakeholder engagement, the main priorities for the next months will be a deep analysis of energy flows in Domaine de la Source and eventual extended measurement, to later conduct a

specific energy community business analysis and define its law feasibility. This development requires both building energy expertise and IT development.

POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS

Polígono Industrial de Las Cabezas can count on the fact that there is a close relationship between energy providers, end users and GFM (as CEC coordinator). GFM is a well-known company in Villacañas and the existing energy services infrastructure is shared by free by GFM. It helps to engage citizens and community members to participate in this project. Also, the CEC will help to inculcate a series of behaviours towards self-consumption installations that will not only help to reduce the electricity bill of each member (or person who has a PV installation) but also minimise the use of energy from the grid and therefore minimise the use of possible fossil fuels when generating energy.

The main issues that were highlighted during the co-creation process were the environmentally sustainable solutions deployment and economical aspects (as a saving tool) to deal with the recent increase in electricity tariffs.

The main objectives in this CEC will be using renewable energy system; boosting e-mobility; showing storage systems as a perfect couple for renewable systems; efficient habits of consumption (not only considering the production of renewable energy, but also considering consuming the energy when is generated or being stored during the non-solar periods.) and driving achievement: reducing electricity dependence and energy and mobility costs.

Although all the services presented in the community have their importance, the main service that brings efficiency to the system is the storage system, as it will help to consume the energy that cannot be consumed at the time it is generated and is perhaps one of the most important services of this pilot thanks to the flexibility it provides.

STAINS CITY

STAINS City will engage to set up two main services: collective-self-consumption and the energy compensation by the hydrogen production and storage. These translate into some specific objectives, such as: compensate electricity and thermal consumption of the demo by the local Production (PV); produce H₂ from the PV panels, store it and use it thanks to the fuel cells; the hybrid heat pumps installed for heating and cooling of the offices, will be exploited to provide the flexibility for improved grid operation; if the parking space owner joins the community, green sources (PV and H₂) will be considered for provision of electricity for recharging 2 EV station.

The co-creation process was very productive but, in many cases, there could be some difficulties to develop some of the emerged ideas within the framework of the NEON project because of some limits, for example the sharing of skills and the fact that some ideas require significant technical and human efforts and cannot be specified in the project times. Next steps will require to define the engagement opportunities to continue the process.

6. Internal Review

6.1. Internal Review 1

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes N= no NA = not applicable

Name of reviewer: Valentina

Organisation: Institute Mihajlo Pupin

Date: 27.05.2022

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
FORMAT: Does the document ... ?				
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?	Y			
... contain a license (in case of public deliverables)?	Y			
... include the names of contributors and reviewers?	Y			
... contain a version table?	Y			
... contain an updated table of contents?	Y			
... contain a list of figures?	Y			
... contain a list of tables?	Y			
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?	Y			
... contain an Executive Summary?	Y			
... contain a Conclusions section?	Y			
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?				Not relevant
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?	Y			

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
... use correct spelling and grammar?	Y			The English can be improved
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes)	Y			
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)	Y			
... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy&paste text)	Y			
About the content...				
Is the deliverable content correctly written?	Y			
Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organized and presented in a logical order?	Y			
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?	Y			
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?	Y			
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?	Y			
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?		N		
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?		N		
Are all references in the document included in the references section?				Not applicable
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (Copy and paste of text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)		N		

SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT
		Added in the text

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

X	Document accepted; no changes required.
	Document accepted; changes required.
	Document not accepted; it must be reviewed after changes are implemented.

Please rank this document globally on a scale of 1-5 (1 = poor, 5= excellent) – using a half point scale. Mark with X the corresponding grade.

Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5
							X	

6.2. Internal Review 2

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes N= no NA = not applicable

Name of reviewer: Eneko Olabarrieta

Organisation: R2M Solution Spain S.L.

Date: 28.05.2022

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
FORMAT: Does the document ... ?				
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?	Y			

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
... contain a license (in case of public deliverables)?	Y			
... include the names of contributors and reviewers?	Y			
... contain a version table?	Y			
... contain an updated table of contents?	Y			
... contain a list of figures?	Y			
... contain a list of tables?	Y			
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?	Y			
... contain an Executive Summary?	Y			
... contain a Conclusions section?	Y			
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?				Not required
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?	Y			
... use correct spelling and grammar?	Y			
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes)		N		
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)	Y			
... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy&paste text)	Y			
About the content...				
Is the deliverable content correctly written?	Y			
Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organized and presented in a logical order?				
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?	Y			

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?	Y			
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?	Y			
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?	Y			
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?		N		
Are all references in the document included in the references section?		N		
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (copy and paste of text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)		N		

SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Document accepted; no changes required.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Document accepted; changes required.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Document not accepted; it must be reviewed after changes are implemented.

Please rank this document globally on a scale of 1-5 (1 = poor, 5= excellent) – using a half point scale. Mark with X the corresponding grade.

Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5
								X

ANNEXES

ANNEX 01

Stakeholders Interviews template (list of annotable questions):

Welcome and introduction (example)

Hello(name of the interviewee)..... My name is(your name), I work for(name of your organization).....

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this interview. As I indicated to you when we made our appointment, we are working on a European project called NEON. This project aims to work on next-generation integrated energy services for citizen energy Communities. As you may know, Citizen Energy Communities are legal entities, made of citizens, cooperatives, local authorities, and enterprises, that team up to produce, consume and sometimes share or sell renewable energies. The(name of the pilot)..... CEC is one of the NEON project pilot / use case.

Therefore we proposed you, as a (potential) member of this future community, to participate in a co-creation process. This collaborative process aims to involve / engage all stakeholders in building the future services of their own community of energy (future CEC); we want to know what could improve your daily routines in relation to energy, and what matters to you in this sense

This will go through two key stages:

- individual interviews with key stakeholders to better know you (your activities, skills, energy uses, needs...),
- then a collaborative workshop with all the CEC stakeholders, during the second half of March (together we will identify common interests and opportunities).

Today, our interview will last about 60 minutes, and will consist of several questions to guide our discussion.

There is no right or wrong answer, please feel free to answer me as you see fit and to share whatever seems relevant.

Before we start, would you be okay with me recording our discussion? It will be useful for me to go back to my note taking if necessary. This recording will not be published or shared with anyone beyond the team working in the project. Once the interview is analyzed, the recording will be deleted.

Part 1 – the stakeholder’s activities and main actors – proposal

Q1 & Q2 - Comment for the interviewer: Dig deep to understand what the stakeholders’ role in the CEC is, how are they related to it, and what activities does she/he do. This will enable us to better understand their motivations and needs.

Q1. My first question is about your main activities and role within the(name of the pilot or location) Building/municipality/neighborhood (depending on the stakeholder).

Answer:

Q2. Generally speaking, what is your relationship with this (place where the CEC will take place)?

Answer:

Q3. What key actors are involved in these activities or have a tight relationship with ... (name of the pilot) ... , employees/ residents / local representatives / authorities / external partner.

Comment to interviewer: It’s important to understand what other key actors they have relationship with, in terms of the CEC pilot.

Answer:

Part 2 – the stakeholder’s services and energy uses – proposal

Q4. What are the services that use energy in your building/municipality/neighborhood?

What are your uses, or in other words, how do you use energy in your day-to-day?

Answer:

Q5. Do you produce renewable energy in this building/municipality/neighborhood and how?

Answer:

Q6. What are the physical means and digital tools you have to produce and/or use and manage energy?

Answer:

Part 3 – Discussion on the stakeholder’s needs and pain points – proposal

Q7. If you had to describe your major pain points in term of energy (access, uses...), what would they be?

Comment to interviewer: Important to reveal what they dislike in their daily routine in relation to energy, it can be in terms of comfort, the electricity bills, the lack of knowledge they have, etc. Make sure you ask follow-up questions to understand **why** they have those pain points.

Answer:

Q8. On the other side, what are you needs and expectations?

Comment to interviewer: It’s sometimes hard for interviewees to locate their needs and expectations, sometimes these are quite hidden. If they have difficulties, ask them about their daily routine and go step by step in their routine to see if she/he can identify needs or aspects that could improve.

Answer:

Q9. Opportunities for the CEC (something you can bring / share or something you would be interested in from other stakeholders)

Answer:

+ Discuss their pain points, needs, expectations and views on possible opportunities related to the CEC.

Other notes from the discussion:

[Acknowledgments and reminder of the next steps](#)

We are coming to the end of this interview. Thank you again.....(name of the interviewee).....for your kind participation.

My notes will be very useful to understand the context of each stakeholder and the possible complementarities. During the collaborative workshop in March, we will discuss the analysis of these interviews as well as the preliminary work of identification and cross-integration of existing services that we carried out in the NEON project, and that are intended to drive an ecological energy transition while improving your comfort and quality of life. Then we will work collaboratively to identify, prioritize, and describe services opportunities for the overall community, touching on social, economic, technological, and environmental aspects.

ANNEX 02

- **CEC 01 -BERCHIDDA services BMCs**

Name of the service	Local Energy Community			
Key partners	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationship	Customers segments
<p>Berchidda Municipality</p> <p>Berchidda's citizens</p> <p>Energy4Com (cooperative)</p> <p>AEC (DSO)</p> <p>GridAbility (service aggregator)</p> <p>Nesosnet (smart meter and the community platform)</p> <p>PROSUME (Prosumer App)</p> <p>R2M Energy (ESCo and energy management services)</p> <p>AXPO (Service provider)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recruitment of members to the CEC (local events to engage citizens at local level and preparation of communication material to be diffused) 2. Energy balance dimensioning of the CEC through surveys, inspections, and collection of members' data (hourly consumption and production for prosumers) 3. Set up of the legal entity for the CEC and official communication from the DSO of the members fo fiscal purposes (incentives) 4. Installation of smart meters (hardware and software part) and connection to PV systems 5. Negotiation with customers for contract offer for renovation works and/or systems' installations 	<p>Set up of social engagement and raise energy consumption and production awareness among Berchidda's citizens.</p> <p>Improve city's buildings energy efficiency.</p> <p>Add value to the town with an additional service to offered to residents and to attract more tourists: EV charging services.</p>	<p>Cooperative model relation through the CEC</p> <p>EPC contracts</p>	<p>The Berchidda CEC members: citizens, the Municipality, the local industries, and SMEs also in the agricultural areas</p> <p>EV owners</p>

<p>6. Installation of technologies (PV systems, Solar thermal systems, HP systems, EV chargers)</p> <p>7. Development of the Prosumer app for enabling CEC selling and purchase transactions</p>	
<p>Key resources</p>	<p>Channels</p>
<p><u>Technical Resources:</u> Prosumer App PV and Solar thermal panels Heat pump systems EV chargers Smart meters Nesosnet Platform</p> <p><u>Human Resources:</u> Equipment suppliers Technical installers Energy experts Legal experts Communication expert Municipality technical office Service providers</p>	<p>For internal communications with the CEC members the Municipality website or telegram chat will be used</p> <p>Newsletters and NEON's website for project's updates</p> <p>Events and workshops</p>
<p>Costs structure</p>	<p>Revenue streams</p>
<p>Development and maintenance of the Prosumer App and Nesosnet Platform Costs related to the Cooperative set up and maintenance Costs related to the formation of the legal entity Installation and maintenance costs of the equipment (PV systems, Solar Thermal systems, heat pumps systems, EV chargers) Device costs (hardware)</p>	<p>The CEC members will pay a one-time fee for joining the cooperative Tax incentives for the collective self-consumption Fee to EV chargers customers</p>

Name of the service		Collective self-consumption of PV production		
Key partners	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationship	Customers segments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Berchidda Municipality Berchidda's citizens Energy4Com (cooperative) AEC (DSO) GridAbility (service aggregator) Nesosnet (smart meter and the community platform) PROSUME (Prosumer App) R2M Energy (ESCo and energy management services) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up of the legal entity for the CEC Installation of smart meters (hardware and software part) and connection to PV systems. The DSO will communicate the members of the community for fiscal purposes (incentives) Development of the Prosumer app for enabling CEC selling and purchase transactions 	Tailor-made energy-sharing service for electricity customers (residential and non-residential) of the Berchidda CEC who have already a PV system installed (prosumer) and only consumers, and which aims to take advantage of national incentives for self-consumption of RES.	Cooperative model relation through the CEC.	The Berchidda CEC members: citizens, the Municipality, the local industries, and SMEs also in the agricultural areas
	Key resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <u>Technical Resources:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prosumer App PV panels Storage batteries Smart meters Nesosnet Platform <u>Human Resources:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical installers Legal experts Communication expert Municipality technical office 		Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Municipality power grid and the Prosumer app. For internal communications with the CEC members the Municipality websites will be used. 	
Costs structure			Revenue streams	

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Development and maintenance of the Prosumer App and Nesosnet Platform• Costs related to the Cooperative set up and maintenance• Costs related to the formation of the legal entity• Installation and maintenance costs of equipment (PV systems and Storage systems)• Device costs (hardware)	<p>National incentive on self-produced and self-consumed energy within the CEC's perimeter</p>
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• **CEC02 -DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE services BMCs**

Name of the service	Power to Grid 100% SELF-CONSUMPTION			
Key partners	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationship	Customers segments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IT development Social skills partner Solar power plant installer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mathematic R&D Promoting self-consumption Web sales channel Web customer relationship & promotion Server maintenance 	Earning money while consuming solar energy guide occupants towards 100% self-consumption	Community development Social relationship between customers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social building owners Existing solar powerplant Solar power plant builders
	Key resources		Self-consumption optimization	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R&D IT dev Web marketing Maintenance team 	Solar power plant installer		
Cost's structure			Revenue streams	
Sales: 100k€ R&D: 100k€ Marketing: 50K€ Support: 50k€			Year 1 : 50K€ - x CeC Year 2 : 100k€ - 40 CeC Year 3 : 200k€ - 80 CeC Year 4 : 400k€ - 160 CeC	

Name of the service	Energy efficiency			
Key partners	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationship	Customers segments

IT dev ESCO Maintenance operator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mathematic R&D • Energy Audit • Measurement 	Energy efficiency Adapting energy systems with flexibility and self consumption	Usage of energy training Technical assistance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social building owners • Cities and territories energy managers • Existing solar powerplant • Solar power plant builders
	Key resources		Channels	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy data analysis • Sensor's installation • Energy engineers' experts • Maintenance team 		Solar power plant installer	
Costs structure			Revenue streams	
Sales: 100k€ R&D ING: 150k€ Maintenance: 100K€ Support: 50k€			Year 1: 50K€ - x CeC Year 2: 100k€ - 40 CeC Year 3: 200k€ - 80 CeC Year 4: 400k€ - 160 CeC	

Name of the service	SOBRIETY			
Key partners	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationship	Customers segments
Sociologist ESCO Engineers	Information and User's follow up	Make users able to understand their energy consumption	Technical & social assistance	Social building owners Solar power plant builders
	Key resources		Channels	
	Energy engineers' experts		Solar power plant installer	

Costs structure	Revenue streams
Sales: 50k€ Technical services: 250k€ Marketing: 0K€ Support: 25k€	Year 1 = 0.5 x structure cost's Year 2 = 1 x structure cost's Year 3 = 1.05 x structure cost's Year 4 = 1.03 x structure cost's

• **CEC 03- POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS services BMCs**

Name of the service	PV SELF CONSUMPTION			
Key partners	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationship	Customers segments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV plant promoters (engineers and installers) • Companies specialized on renewable energy • Energetic services providers • Legal experts • Platform developers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEC constitution: • PV modules and inverters installation • System legalization (agreements with the grid company and administration). • Self-consumption activity for sharing energy with CEC members. • Virtual Energy Balance to provide energy to consumers who are not directly connected to PV systems. • Set up the platform for monitoring and managing CEC. • Cost solidarity policy between stakeholders 	<p>Electricity environmentally sustainable</p> <p>Strategies for an efficient way of consumption habits</p> <p>Reduction of net electricity bill</p> <p>Recharging services for portable energy package solutions (storage) to make possible to carry electricity to off grid sites (field, forest, etc.).</p>	<p>CEC and the entity managing CEC.</p> <p>The collaboration agreement of CEC.</p> <p>Periodically assemblies</p>	<p>Consumers directly connected to PV systems</p> <p>Consumers not directly connected to PV systems</p> <p>Consumers who enjoy time who are present in off grid sites.</p>
	Key resources		Channels	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV modules • PV inverters • Electrical material • E-meters • Monitoring and management platform • Human Resources (marketing, communication, engineering, CEC management) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power Grid and Market electricity agent • Monitoring and management system • Newsletter • Emails • Periodically workshops for stakeholders • Dissemination • Periodically assemblies (CEC) • Training seminars for people who manage CEC • Seminars for efficient habits of consumption 	
<p>Costs structure</p>			<p>Revenue streams</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PV modules and PV inverters (the effort depends on financial model) • E-meters (for virtual energy balance) • Managing and monitoring platform for energy community (CEC) • Taxes and fees for legalization • Managing costs (personal, fees, etc.) • Association constitution. 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fee from end users • Revenues from surplus energy generation fed into the grid • Saving money from directly self-consumption (directly end users connected to PV plant) 	

Name of the service	STORAGE									
Key partners	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationship	Customers segments						
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Storage promoters (engineers and installers) Companies specialized on renewable energy Energetic services providers Legal experts Platform developers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CEC constitution Batteries and inverters/chargers installation System legalization (agreements with the grid company and administration). Self-consumption activity for sharing energy with CEC members. Virtual Energy Balance to provide energy to consumers who are not directly connected to storage systems. Set up the platform for monitoring and managing CEC. Cost solidarity policy between stakeholders <table border="1" data-bbox="426 906 852 1398"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="426 906 852 967">Key resource</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="426 967 852 1398"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Batteries Inverters / chargers Electrical material E-meters Monitoring and management platform Human Resources (marketing, communication, engineering, CEC management) </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Key resource	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Batteries Inverters / chargers Electrical material E-meters Monitoring and management platform Human Resources (marketing, communication, engineering, CEC management) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better use of surplus photovoltaic generation Strategies for an efficient way of consumption habits Reduction of net electricity bill Recharging services for portable energy package solutions (storage) to make possible to carry electricity to off grid sites (field, forest, etc.). 	<table border="1" data-bbox="1129 342 1509 1398"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="1129 342 1509 906">Customer relationship</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="1129 342 1509 906"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CEC and the entity managing CEC. The collaboration agreement of CEC. Periodically assemblies </td> </tr> <tr> <th data-bbox="1129 906 1509 967">Channels</th> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1129 967 1509 1398"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Power Grid and Market electricity agent Monitoring and management system Newsletter Emails Periodically workshops for stakeholders Dissemination Periodically assemblies (CEC) Training seminars for people who manage CEC </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Customer relationship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CEC and the entity managing CEC. The collaboration agreement of CEC. Periodically assemblies 	Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Power Grid and Market electricity agent Monitoring and management system Newsletter Emails Periodically workshops for stakeholders Dissemination Periodically assemblies (CEC) Training seminars for people who manage CEC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consumers directly connected to storage systems Consumers not directly connected to storage systems Consumers who enjoy time who are present in off grid sites.
Key resource										
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seminars for efficient habits of consumption 	
Costs structure			Revenue streams	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Batteries and inverter/chargers (the effort depends on financial model) • E-meters (for virtual energy balance) • Managing and monitoring platform for energy community (CEC) • Taxes and fees for legalization • Managing costs (personal, fees, etc.) • Association constitution. 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fee from end users • Saving money from directly self-consumption (directly end users connected to storage plant) 	

Name of the service	EV RECHARGING STATION			
Key partners	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationship	Customers segments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EV recharging station promoters (engineers and installers) • Energy efficiency companies • Energy services providers • Legal experts • Platform developers • Payment platform developers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEC constitution • EV recharging station installation • System legalization (agreements with the grid company and administration). • Recharging services for external users of CEC • Recharging services for CEC members • Virtual energy balance for CEC members • Set up the platform for monitoring and managing CEC. • Cost solidarity policy between stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emission free mobility. • Reduction of fuel needs. • Electric load which allows more integration from renewable energy. • Strategies for an efficient way of driving habits • Reduction of mobility needs costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEC and the entity managing CEC. • The collaboration agreement of CEC. • Periodically assemblies 	<p>EV vehicles owners</p>
	<p>Key resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electric vehicles • EV recharging stations • Payment platform • Electrical material • E-meters • Monitoring and management platform • Human Resources (marketing, communication, engineering, CEC management) 		<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power Grid and Market electricity agent • Energy provider payment platform • Monitoring and management system • Newsletter • Emails • Periodically workshops for stakeholders • Dissemination • Periodically assemblies (CEC) • Training seminars for people who manage CEC • Seminars for efficient habits of driving 	

Costs structure	Revenue streams
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• EV recharging station (the effort depends on financial model)• Price of electricity demand• Costs related to energy provider payment platform• E-meters (for virtual energy balance)• Managing and monitoring platform for energy community (CEC)• Taxes and fees for legalization• Managing costs (personal, fees, etc.)• Association constitution.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Fee from end users• Income from recharging services (CEC members)• Income from recharging services (not CEC members)

• **CEC 04 -STAINS CITY services BMCs**

Name of the service		collective self-consumption		
Key partners	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationship	Customers segments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DSO: ENEDIS • Legal and operational experts for setting up the CEC, • Monitoring platform editor. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation and management of the CEC • Modification of the ENEDIS connection to be able to inject the surplus (surplus to be sold by INDUSTREET/integrated into the scope of a balance manager) • Automate the energy sharing / injection of surplus on the power grid, • Implementation of the CEC members' service distribution key, • Select and set up the monitoring and management platform, • Prepare and distribute the CEC communication materials. 	<p>Provide STAIN CITY CEC the surplus photovoltaic produced by INDUSTREET panels to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share a renewable and clean energy to use according to their needs, • Enable them to better manage their energy consumption and save money, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen Energy Community Corporation body- status of the Association - establishment of CEC board. 	<p>CEC members, currently including ENGIE Corp research center CRIGEN Lab and the innovative training campus INDUSTREET.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need: decarbonization of the site / renewable energy sources, control of the bill... • Pain: production of Hydrogen from fossil fuels
	Key resources			

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human resources and skills: members of the corporation body, lawyers, network and telecommunication experts, monitoring platform maintenance experts, communication, and marketing, • Technical resources: photovoltaic panels, power and telecommunication network, monitoring platform. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communications (mails, newsletters, Intranet...) within CEC members (internal sites and Group level), • Collective self-consumption monitoring platform, 	
Cost structure			Revenue streams	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The expert legal and operational support for setting up the CEC, • Filing the CEC legal status, • DSO Fees related to the power grid connection, • Access to the monitoring platform (licenses, annual cost, admin vs. users...) including problem solving, maintenance, evolutions, • Photovoltaic infrastructure amortization. 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreement within the CEC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> hypo. 1: re-invoicing between members hypo. 2: energy exchange (electricity created by CRIGEN from Hydrogen) • Repurchase of the remaining surplus (after self-consumption within the CEC) by the balance manager. 	

Name of the service		Energy electricity compensation with H2 storage during the off PV production period.		
Key partners	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationship	Customers segments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hydrogen Lab ENGIE • DSO: ENEDIS • Legal and operational experts for setting up the CEC, • Monitoring platform editor. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation, storage H2 and production of electricity via the fuel cells, • Creation and management of the CEC • Modification of the ENEDIS connection to be able to inject the surplus (surplus to be sold by INDUSTREET/integrated into the scope of a balance manager) • Automate the energy sharing / injection of surplus on the power grid, • Select and set up the monitoring and management platform, • Prepare and distribute the CEC communication materials. 	<p>Provide STAIN CITY CEC the production of Hydrogen produced and stored from INDUSTREET photovoltaic surplus production to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • allow CEC members to benefit from renewable energy to be used according to their needs, in particular off PV production period (night, etc.), • enable them to better manage their energy consumption and save money, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen Energy Community • Corporation body- status of the Association - establishment of CEC board. 	<p>CEC members, currently including ENGIE Corp research center CRIGEN Lab and the innovative training campus INDUSTREET.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need: decarbonization of the site / renewable energy sources, control of the bill... • Pain: production of Hydrogen from fossil fuels, limitation of PV production and impossibility of use for needs Off the PV production period (e.g., Air Handling Unit AHU at night)
	Key resources		Channels	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human resources and skills: members of the corporation body, lawyers, network and telecommunication experts, monitoring platform maintenance experts, 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communications (mails, newsletters, Intranet...) within CEC members (internal sites and Group level), • Collective self-consumption monitoring platform. 	

	<p>communication, and marketing,</p> <p>Technical resources: photovoltaic panels, H2chain, power and telecommunication network, monitoring platform.</p>			
<p>Cost structure</p>			<p>Revenue streams</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The expert legal and operational support for setting up the CEC, • Filing the CEC legal status, • DSO Fees related to the power grid connection, • Access to the monitoring platform (licenses, annual cost, admin vs. users...) including problem solving, maintenance, evolutions, • Cost of the H2 chain: Production, Storage, generation, Fuel cell 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreement within the CEC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> hypo. 1: re-invoicing between members hypo. 2: energy exchange (Surplus of PV production produced by INDUSTREET) 	

Name of the service		HVAC system optimization and control		
Key partners	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationship	Customers segments
BMS manufacturers and integrators Mtair Solutherm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deployment of the tool that optimize the energy and thermal behavior of the building, • Interconnection with the BMS of the building • Collection of data • Production of pre-heating / cooling schedules • Production of dashboards • after-sales service • Tool maintenance / evolution 	<p>Optimize the operation of the HVAC system to reduce consumption while ensuring the occupant comfort.</p> <p>...Thanks to the occupancy prediction in the different areas of the building to optimize pre-heating/cooling and heating/cooling periods according to arrival and presence times.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen Energy Community • Corporation body- status of the Association - establishment of CEC board. 	<p>CEC members, currently including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The facility manager responsible on the building operation and maintenance. needs: to have solutions to automatically adjust the heating and cooling system according occupants' requirements. pains: acquire all the I individual requests, manually check the controllers in each area one by one, lack of visibility on certain controllers • The occupants of the ENGIE building: needs: maintaining a certain level of comfort / good working conditions while optimizing energy consumption. pains: lack of efficiency of the heating and cooling system in certain areas.
	Key resources	Centralization of information and KPIs to facilitate the building exploitation.	Channels	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human resources and skills: facility manager, developers, BMS experts, aggregator. • Technical resources: IT infrastructure, BMS, dashboards. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication between the platform and the BMS, • Dashboard available to the facility manager. 		
Cost structure			Revenue streams	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human resources (development, after-sales service, etc.) • BMS integrator services • IT infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Savings on the energy bill • Reuse of the service and algorithms in a business context outside CEC.
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Name of the service		EV charging from clean resources		
Key partners	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationship	Customers segments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parking space promoter • Manufacturer/ supplier and installer of the charging stations, • Solution editor for the EV charging control (technical, digital, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of contracts and existing specifications, • Share the production of renewable energies with sharing station, • Determine the distribution keys to share the local energy production (from PV or fuel cells) • Develop the management and the planning of the EV charging (opportunity time to load / unload EVs) • Create specific media for each use (training, availability for recharging, etc.) and promote the service, • Set up the monitoring and supervision platform for the charging station, • Create the agreement with public and private entities to benefit from this service. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EVs charging stations from renewable energies and available for the needs and usage of the CEC (charging VE, training, etc.) • Provide flexibility to CEC by allowing the use EVs charged with excess PV energy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen Energy Community • Corporation body - status of the Association - establishment of CEC board, • Agreements with private and public entities. 	<p>CEC members, currently including currently</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENGIE employees (4 charging stations already available in the parking space. <p>Needs: recharging EVs via green energy sources (surplus PV or hydrogen)</p> <p>Pain: today electricity comes from the supplier (non-renewable + cost) + no use to date</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The instructors, employees, and trainees of the INDUSTREET training campus: <p>Needs: use for maintenance operations and training around the terminal</p>

	<p>Key resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human resources and skills: Parking space promoter, Manufacturer/ supplier, installer of the charging stations, instructor (for training), developers, communication expert, legal experts. • Technical resources: Charging station, IT infrastructure, monitoring, and supervision platform, PV/H2 production, energy contracts. 		<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EV charging stations, • Support specific to each use (training / Use) • EV station management platform, • Eventually, communication with nearby entities interested in this kind of services. 	<p>Pain: not have a fleet of EVs to perform this kind of operations, problem of maturity at the level of the sector</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private and public entities that have EVs in the district area. <p>Needs: find accessible EV charging station in the district area without having to invest.</p> <p>Pain: investment related to EV charging station installation.</p>
<p>Cost structure</p>			<p>Revenue streams</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NDUSTREET PV infrastructure amortization, • Energy transformation and redistribution by ENGIE, • Legal and juridical expertise, • Creation of training supports and media • Creation of communication/promotion media • Purchase / implementation / maintenance of digital solutions (monitoring platform... 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy bill reduction • New covered period to use green energy off PV production period, • Payment for parking access and the EV charging service, • -Ultimately contribution by users (local authorities, etc.). 	